

D6.3 – CROPS MOOC for Educators and Students

December 2025

European Schoolnet® (EUN)

Document Details	
Project Acronym / Name	CROPS: Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe
Project URL	http://crops-cs.eu
Project Type	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
EU Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Grant Agreement No.	101131696
Project Start Date	1 January 2024
Project End Date	31 December 2026
Work Package	WP6 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
Deliverable	D6.3
Deliverable Due Date	31/12/2025
Actual Submission Date	18/12/2025
Lead Beneficiary for this Deliverable	European Schoolnet (EUN)
Reviewed by	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Earthwatch
Revision	1.0
Dissemination level	Public
Number of pages	158

To cite this document

European Schoolnet (2025). D6.3 – CROPS MOOC for Educators and Students. *Deliverable report of project Horizon Europe CROPS (grant agreement No. 101131696)*.

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable we present the *CROPS MOOC – From Classroom to Impact: Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science*, developed under Work Package 6 of the Horizon Europe CROPS project and delivered through the European Schoolnet® Academy with the support of Scientix®. The course aimed to empower educators to integrate citizen science into their teaching practice while connecting classroom learning to the five EU Missions.

The MOOC, delivered from 13 October to 19 November 2025, attracted **508 educators, reaching indirectly more than 6,100 students**. The course had a 54% completion rate.

In this document we outline the design and delivery of the MOOC, including its preparation, launch, and live components; the dissemination and communication activities supporting its uptake; the characteristics and engagement of participants; and the feedback collected through pre- and post-course evaluation. We also synthesise the overall outcomes, present the CROPS Learning Scenarios and provide the full course content as an Annex.

Evaluation findings indicate a strong positive impact on participants. **96% rated the course as “Good” or “Very good,”** and **97% reported increased confidence in involving their students in citizen science projects**. Qualitative feedback highlights the practical relevance, immediate applicability, and overall usefulness of the course materials.

Overall, the CROPS MOOC achieved its objectives and strengthened educators’ capacity to involve students in citizen science activities, thereby contributing to the wider CROPS ambition of supporting the uptake and impact of citizen science across Europe.

The complete text and materials developed for the MOOC, were released under a CC-BY licence. This open licence enables anyone to reuse, adapt, and build upon the content. Making the material openly accessible enhances the long-term sustainability of the course and supports wider uptake and reuse across education and citizen science.

All course materials and resources will remain available on the European Schoolnet Academy platform, although participants can no longer receive certification.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The CROPS project and the *From Classroom to Impact: Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science MOOC*

CROPS¹ aims to support the transition of citizen science from small-scale initiatives to activities with Europe-wide reach, advancing a modern, open-science approach. The project will identify the most suitable citizen science initiatives for upscaling and, in the process, develop protocols, resources, and examples of best practice to help practitioners maximise the impact of their work in relation to the Horizon Europe EU Missions. This support will be tailored to different types of citizen science and the diverse stakeholders involved.

CROPS will also help practitioners consider inclusivity, public trust, and societal impact, while taking into account requirements related to data interoperability, sustainability, and funding when expanding their activities.

These goals will be pursued through four interconnected strands of work:

- i. assessing existing citizen science practices, their activities, and their suitability for upscaling;
- ii. creating protocols and guidance for upscaling citizen science, building on and replicating existing best practices;
- iii. providing advice on practical considerations such as open data sharing, sustainability, responsible research and innovation (RRI), and diverse funding opportunities; and
- iv. developing transnational citizen science communities by establishing societal coalitions and identifying potential citizen science champions to raise awareness of the role citizen science can play in addressing the Horizon Europe EU Mission objectives.

Within this framework, the CROPS MOOC for Educators and Students (D6.3), developed under WP6 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, and supported by Scientix®, was designed to enable educators and, through them, their students to fully realise the potential of citizen science and the CROPS project outputs. The MOOC attracted around 500 participants, indirectly reaching over 6,000 students. According to data from the pre- and post-course surveys, 96% of participants rated the overall value of the course as “Good” or “Very good,” and 97% reported that they intend to use the ideas and examples presented.

¹ To learn more about CROPS, visit the website: <https://crops-cs.eu/>

This document provides an overview of the MOOC's development and implementation, including information on the European Schoolnet Academy, the course content and structure, dissemination activities, participant profiles, collected feedback, and overall conclusions.

1.2 The European Schoolnet® Academy

The European Schoolnet Academy was launched in 2014 in response to the need to scale up professional development opportunities for teachers and support them in addressing the growing number of challenges they face in the classroom. The Academy primarily offers massive open online courses (MOOCs), which are entirely free of charge and open to anyone, with no limit on the number of participants. This focus on openness, and the pedagogical approach that accompanies it, is based on three premises:

- i. The need to cost-effectively scale professional development offers to larger numbers of teachers, giving more educators the opportunity to access and benefit from them.
- ii. The conviction that teachers should be self-reflective practitioners, willing to interact with peers and demonstrating a high level of self-efficacy.
- iii. The recognition, supported by research, that successful professional development fosters learning communities in which teachers share their expertise.

The European Schoolnet Academy courses target teachers and other education professionals such as head teachers, ICT coordinators, and school counsellors. The potential outreach of a course depends on the design of its activities, the target audience, and the dissemination strategies used. A typical course on the Academy attracts between 300 and 2,000 teachers, depending on the topic and target group.

Participant engagement extends well beyond those formally enrolled, as a significant amount of course-related activity takes place across various social media channels. A typical course tweet reaches close to 100,000 Twitter profiles, and dissemination by European Schoolnet's Ministries of Education further enhances visibility within national education communities.

The MOOCs offered through the European Schoolnet Academy run for a limited time, are fully tutored, and award digital badges and certificates upon successful completion. They follow a connectivist and collaborative approach and include peer assessment between teachers. In 2023, the

Academy achieved an average course engagement rate of 68% and a completion rate of 43% across 10 MOOCs².

1.3 Scientix[®]

Scientix³ is Europe's leading community for science education, coordinated by European Schoolnet. For over 14 years, it has supported the advancement of STEM education by connecting teachers, schools, policymakers, researchers, and industry partners.

Scientix focuses on four key priorities, developed together with the Ministries of Education STEM Representatives Working Group:

- Improving STEM education at all levels;
- Linking STEM learning to global challenges;
- Widening access to STEM careers;
- Strengthening exchange and peer learning among educators.

These priorities are implemented through a wide range of projects and initiatives addressing topics such as environmental education, integrated STEM teaching, and classroom innovation. Scientix also fosters collaboration through programmes such as:

- the Scientix Ambassadors, supporting teacher exchange and peer learning;
- the STEM School Label, helping schools develop and validate their STEM strategy;
- the STEM Alliance, connecting educators with industry partners.

Through its portal, Scientix provides thousands of STEM education resources, tools, articles, and training opportunities through its repositories, promoting a shared, co-creative approach to improving STEM education across Europe.

2 MOOC Preparation, Launch and Live Events

The CROPS MOOC *From Classroom to Impact: Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science* took place between October 13 and November 19, 2025. The course was promoted and co-organised by Scientix.

² Bilgin, A. S., & Hertz, B. (2024). *EUN Academy Evaluation Report 2023, European Schoolnet Academy*. European Schoolnet. <http://www.eun.org/resources/detail?publicationID=2601>

³ To learn more about Scientix, visit the website: <https://www.scientix.eu/>

In Table 1 we provide the course structure and the opening date of each module.

Table 1: Structure of the course and opening dates

Module	Title	Opening date
Module 1	<i>Introduction to citizen science and the five EU Missions</i>	13/10/2025
Module 2	<i>Choosing the right citizen science project for your students</i>	20/10/2025
Module 3	<i>Planning and implementing citizen science activities</i>	27/10/2025
Module 4	<i>Assessing students' learning and impact of citizen science projects</i>	03/11/2025

Participants had, on average, one week to complete the expected workload for each module, carry out the activities, and engage in course discussions. Throughout the course, they developed a Learning Scenario, with each module providing guidance, examples, and support for completing specific sections. After the end of Week 4, participants were given an additional one and a half weeks to finalise their Learning Scenario – required for certification – which integrated a citizen science project of their choice (addressing one of the five EU Missions) and included reviewing and providing feedback on the Learning Scenarios of three fellow MOOC participants.

During the MOOC, two live events took place:

- **Scientix® & CROPS Webinar: Meet the CROPS Citizen Science Champions⁴** (15/10/2025) – featuring one CROPS Citizen Science Champion representative for each of the five EU Missions (refer to Figure 1 for the promo visual).
- **TeachMeet⁵** (06/11/2025) – a session where teachers shared activities and best practices for engaging students in citizen science projects.

The MOOC content is provided in the annex of this report and can also be accessed via the following link:

⁴ More information about the event, including the recording and the presenters' slides, is available on the Scientix website: <https://www.scientix.eu/resources/pd-resources/webinars/webinar?id=2064787>

⁵ The TeachMeet recording and the presenters' slides are available on the CROPS MOOC platform.

<https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:CROPS+CitizenScience+2025/>

Figure 1: CROPS MOOC webinar promo visual

2.1 The CROPS & Scientix Learning Scenarios

To provide MOOC participants with examples on how citizen science can be integrated into teaching and learning activities, five Learning Scenarios were developed by European Schoolnet in collaboration with five educators (Scientix Ambassadors) – one targeting each EU mission. For the Soil, Cancer, and Water missions, we selected projects identified in D2.2 (Scalability Ranking Report): **LandPKS**, **Foldit**, and **Marine Debris Tracker**, respectively.

For the other two missions, we opted for projects outside the list to:

- i. Show educators that there are more than the 500 shortlisted projects, and that they should feel comfortable reviewing projects that better fit their programmes, schools, or classes.
- ii. Show examples similar to the shortlisted ones but based in Europe, to maximise the likelihood of uptake by teachers by selecting projects already embedded in European contexts and available in multiple languages (e.g., **Mosquito Alert** for the Climate Adaptation mission).
- iii. Include an example of a project with no educational resources to encourage educators to be the change in those projects (e.g., **Our Outdoors** for the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities mission).

All Learning Scenarios are available on the Scientix portal to maximise uptake among STEM educators across Europe and extend their reach beyond MOOC participants. For a more detailed overview, you can access them through the links below (Table 2) and consult the related news item published on Scientix (<https://www.scientix.eu/news-events/news/article?id=2066538>).

Table 2: CROPS & Scientix Learning Scenarios

Learning Scenario Title	Mission	Project	Link
Tiger Mosquito Detectives: A Citizen Science Challenge	Adaptation to climate change	Mosquito Alert	https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131020
Curly or Straight? Learning Protein Structure through Foldit and Citizen Science	Cancer	Foldit	https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131002
Evaluating Urban Public Spaces: A Citizen Science Approach With Our Outdoors	Climate-neutral and smart cities	Our Outdoors	https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131021
Is Our Schoolyard Soil Healthy? Investigating Soil Properties Using the LandPKS App	A soil deal for Europe	LandPKS App	https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131003
Waters in Our Hands: A Citizen Science Journey with Marine Debris Tracker	Restore our oceans and waters	Marine Debris Tracker	https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131022

3 Dissemination Package and Communication Activities

Several dissemination activities were planned and carried out to promote the MOOC.

The promotional materials included visuals, messages, videos, and one-pagers. Key information about the MOOC promotion is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: CROPS MOOC Promotional Information

Promotion dates	From June to October 2025
Promo pack & sign up	https://www.scientix.eu/resources/pd-resources/moocs/crops-mooc-2025
Promo video URL	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QL11rwtr2OY
Course hashtag	#cropsCSMOOC
Project handle/hashtag	@cropsCS, @eu_schoolnet, @scientix_eu, #cropsCSMOOC,
Service hashtag	#EUNAcademy

The complete promotional package can be accessed here: <https://files.eun.org/scientix/CROPS-MOOC-Promo-Pack-Final.pdf>

The MOOC was widely promoted on X (Figure 2), Facebook (Figure 4), LinkedIn (Figure 5), and Instagram (Figure 3) by CROPS and Scientix. Examples of dissemination messages are provided below.

Figure 2: Example of X post promoting the course

Figure 4: Example of Facebook post promoting the course

Figure 5: Example of LinkedIn post promoting the course

Figure 3: Example of Instagram post promoting the course

In addition, a one-pager (Figure 6) was created and disseminated through CROPS and Scientix social media:

crops **European Schoolnet Academy** **SCIENTIX**
The community for science education in Europe

FROM CLASSROOM TO IMPACT:

Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science MOOC

What if your students could test air quality, monitor ocean pollution, or analyse cancer data – all while contributing to real-world scientific research?

This MOOC helps educators bring citizen science into their teaching and contribute to key EU Missions: climate, cancer, oceans, smart cities, and soil.

Join this course and:

- Learn the basics of citizen science.
- Explore and connect with active citizen science projects.
- Discover practical ways to integrate them into your lessons.
- Inspire your students to help solve some of Europe's biggest challenges.

Key Info:

- **Course Dates:** 13 October – 19 November 2025 (5.5 weeks).
- **Estimated Effort:** 16 – 20 hours (3 – 5 hours per module).
- **Spread the Word:** Download the dissemination pack [here!](#)

ENROLL NOW

AND START YOUR JOURNEY FROM CLASSROOM TO IMPACT!

#cropsCSMOOC #cropsCS

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 6: MOOC one-pager

A news item about the MOOC was published on the Scientix website (<https://www.scientix.eu/news-events/news/article?id=2003464>), and information about the course was also shared through several newsletters, including the Scientix Digest (4,515 subscribers), European Schoolnet’s Teachers Newsletter (4,651 subscribers), and the CROPS Newsletter (110 subscribers).

The MOOC was additionally featured in an episode of Scientix TV: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H8vIZ7b7SVw>

Finally, the MOOC was also presented in an online event organised by the eTwinning STEM Teachers Group on September 2025, which was attended by 20 teachers.

4 Profile of Participants

Overall, 1061 people from 69 countries registered to take part in the MOOC, **508 people took part in the course⁶, reaching over 6,100 students indirectly**. Furthermore, 275 participants completed the course⁷, achieving **an engagement rate at 48%⁸ and a completion rate at 54%⁹**. The completion rate is higher than that reported for all EUN Academy courses taking place in 2023, suggesting that participants were particularly engaged with the content of the course.

In the map (Figure 7), the countries of origin for participants from EUN member countries are displayed.

Figure 7: Number of participants from EUN member countries

⁶ A person is counted as a participant if the person has completed at least one activity in the course in any module.

⁷ A participant is counted as a completer if the participant has explored all the sections of the MOOC and did all the activities.

⁸ The course engagement rate is calculated by dividing the number of participants who completed at least one section of the course by the total number of people who registered to the course.

⁹ The course completion rate is calculated by dividing the total number of participants who completed at least one section of the MOOC) by the total number of participants that completed the course.

Table 4 provides an overview of **the top 10 countries** by the number of participants in the MOOC, along with the number of participants who successfully completed the course.

Table 4: Top 10 countries by number of participants that participated in and completed the MOOC

Top 10 countries by number of participants that:			
Participated in the MOOC		Completed the MOOC	
Turkey	125	Turkey	63
Romania	84	Romania	54
Greece	82	Greece	53
Croatia	42	Croatia	28
Italy	40	Italy	22
Spain	33	Spain	18
Portugal	16	Portugal	7
North Macedonia	9	North Macedonia	7
Albania	7	Serbia	3
Belgium	6	Bulgaria	2

Before the course launch, a questionnaire was distributed to all participants to gather insights into their backgrounds, including current position (Figure 8), gender (Figure 9), age (Figure 10), and years of experience in the education sector (Figure 11). The survey revealed that most participants are female, aged 36 or older, and work as secondary school teachers. Other roles held by course participants include primary school teachers, pre-primary (early childhood education and care) teachers, non-formal (adult) educators, teacher trainers, and heads of school. Half of the participants had more than 20 years of experience in the educational field.

Figure 8: Participants' background

Figure 9: Participants' gender

Figure 10: Participants' age

Figure 11: Participants' years of experience in education

5 Participants Feedback and Course Impression

After the course concluded, an evaluation questionnaire was automatically made available on the EUN Academy course platform to collect information and insights about participants’ experiences during the MOOC. For the question regarding the overall value of the course, **96% of the 83 participants** who responded rated it as **“Very good”** or **“Good”** (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Participants' perception of course value

Participants were very satisfied with the course. Specifically, **89% said they would take a similar course again**, **91% agreed that the course discussions were useful** for their learning, and **92% felt the course quality met their expectations** (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Participants' evaluation of course discussions, quality, and future enrolment in similar courses

Regarding the impact of the MOOC on participants' professional practice, **86%** of respondents reported that they **have already used ideas from the course** in their teaching, **97% feel more confident in involving their students in citizen science projects**, **99% indicate an improved ability to reflect on their own practice**, and **97% intend to apply the ideas and examples presented in the course** in their everyday work (Figure 14). These results suggest that the MOOC effectively enhanced participants' confidence in implementing citizen science activities, encouraged practical application of citizen science projects in the classroom, and supported their professional development as educators committed to engaging students in meaningful scientific inquiry.

Figure 14: Participants' assessment of the course impact on their professional practice

Additionally, participants were asked to self-assess their competence in addressing citizen science before and after completing the course. The results show a clear upward shift in confidence and perceived competence. After the course, the proportion of participants who felt they had a **good knowledge of citizen science and were ready to implement it in practice** rose sharply from **7.5%** to **33.7%**. Even more notably, those who reported having **strong knowledge and practical experience**, and felt confident **advising or guiding others**, increased from **6.3%** to **34.9%**.

At the same time, the share of participants who previously reported **limited familiarity** with the topic decreased substantially. Those who said they **knew only some basics** dropped from **40.0%** before the course to **9.6%** after, while those who had merely **heard about citizen science and wanted to learn the basics** declined from **21.3%** to **13.3%**. Similarly, participants who

had **good knowledge but needed practical guidance** fell from **25.0%** to **8.4%** (Figure 15).

Overall, these findings indicate that the course effectively strengthened participants’ understanding of citizen science and significantly enhanced their readiness to apply and support it in their professional practice.

Figure 15: Pre-to-post change in self-assessed competence in integrating citizen science into teaching

Besides responding to standard survey questions, participants had the opportunity to provide personalized feedback through open-ended questions.

Some positive comments from participants included:

“The most enjoyable part was exploring real citizen science projects and discussing how to implement them in the classroom.”

“It showed me how to integrate classroom activity with real science research!”

“While participating in this course, I particularly enjoyed the citizen science projects that involved students developing solutions to real-world problems and experiencing scientific processes. The STEM-focused, interdisciplinary approach and opportunities to use technology effectively were also quite engaging.”

“I really enjoyed how practical the course was. Everything felt immediately applicable in the classroom, and the mix of citizen science, inquiry-based learning, and real data made the experience surprisingly energising.”

“The course was very enjoyable and productive. I learned a lot of good information and I will put what I learned into practice with my students.”

Some suggestions for improvement included:

“I think it is well-structured but I would have liked a messaging board or a chat with questions to moderators throughout the course.”

“More examples can be uploaded.”

“More TeachMeets.”

“Some more time – it was really packed!”

“I think there should be language options.”

6 Conclusion

The results highlight the strong impact of the CROPS MOOC on educators, with 508 participants indirectly reaching over 6,100 students.

Participants reported increased knowledge, confidence, and competence in implementing citizen science projects, with 97% intending to apply course ideas in their practice. Feedback emphasized the course’s practical relevance, engaging format, and opportunities to connect classroom activities to real scientific research. Suggestions for improvement included more interactivity, additional examples, and multilingual options. Overall, the MOOC effectively empowered educators to involve students in meaningful citizen science activities and strengthen their scientific inquiry skills.

In the Annex we provide the complete text and materials developed for the MOOC, released under a CC-BY licence. This open licence enables anyone to reuse, adapt, and build upon the content. Making the material openly accessible enhances the long-term sustainability of the course and supports wider uptake and reuse across education and citizen science.

All course materials and resources will remain available on the European Schoolnet Academy platform¹⁰, although participants can no longer receive certification since the course ended on 19 November 2025.

¹⁰ <https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:CROPS+CitizenScience+2025/>

Annex: Welcome to the CROPS MOOC – From Classroom to Impact: Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science

Young people spend a large part of their lives in school – but too often, what they learn in science feels disconnected from the world around them. Experiments are often predictable, results discarded, and concepts can seem distant from everyday life. But what if their efforts truly mattered? What if the data they gathered helped advance scientific research and tackle real-world problems? That’s the power of citizen science. Anyone, anywhere – including you and your students – can take part in meaningful research and make a difference.

This course is open to educators who want to bring real-world science into the classroom through citizen science. You’ll explore inspiring citizen science projects, learn how they connect to the EU’s five Missions – climate, cancer, oceans, smart cities, and soil – and discover ways to bring them into your teaching. The course is flexible and easy to follow, with one module released weekly and a single deadline for submitting your Learning Scenario and peer review.

Imagine your students monitoring ocean pollution, tracking local wildlife, testing air quality, analysing cancer data, or examining soil health nearby – all while contributing to real research.

Let's make it happen. Start your journey from classroom to impact!

Join us in the [Facebook group](#) or share your thoughts on X (formerly Twitter) using the hashtag [#cropsCSMOOC](#).

Learning Objectives

After completing the MOOC, you will:

- Explain the core principles of citizen science and its value for science, society and student learning.
- Evaluate citizen science projects using a variety of criteria to determine their relevance and suitability for your teaching context.
- Investigate how citizen science supports and connects to the five EU Missions: oceans, smart cities, cancer, climate, and soil.
- Select a citizen science project and explore how students can meaningfully contribute to an EU Mission through their participation.
- Design a Learning Scenario based on an active citizen science project and the scientific inquiry process.

Prerequisites

This course is designed for primary and secondary school teachers, as well as educators at other levels. It may also interest teacher trainers, student teachers, researchers, citizen science project coordinators, and anyone curious about or involved in citizen science.

Modules

- Module 1: *Introduction to Citizen Science and the Five EU Missions* opens on 13/10/2025
- Module 2: *Choosing the Right Citizen Science Project for Your Students* opens on 20/10/2025
- Module 3: *Planning and Implementing Citizen Science Activities* opens on 27/10/2025
- Module 4: *Assessing Students' Learning and Impact of Citizen Science Projects* opens on 03/11/2025

Certification

To earn a course certificate, you need to submit a Learning Scenario and review three Learning Scenarios from other participants. The overall passing grade is **95%**.

The final deadline to complete all activities is **19 November 2025, 23:59 CET**.

*If you have completed the MOOC and you're interested in applying to be a **Scientix Ambassador**, make sure to follow our news and updates. This MOOC is one of the requirements for the Scientix Ambassador application. More information about the upcoming call for new Scientix Ambassadors will be published soon in the [Scientix Community Tool](#) and in the [Scientix Digest](#). Be sure to activate your profile in the Scientix Community Tool and to subscribe to the Scientix Digest so you don't miss out!*

Note to teachers from Galicia: *Se es profesor/a de Galicia e, aparte do certificado da European Schoolnet Academy, queres recibir a certificación oficial de parte da Consellería de Educación, Ciencia, Universidades e Formación Profesional, inscríbete en FPROFE: <https://www.edu.xunta.gal/fprofe/>*

Note to teachers from Emilia-Romagna: *Per i docenti della regione Emilia-Romagna iscritti alla piattaforma regionale <https://iscrizioni.istruzioneer.it/> è possibile ottenere, oltre all'attestato rilasciato da European Schoolnet Academy, anche l'attestato rilasciato dall'Ufficio Scolastico Regionale per l'Emilia-Romagna (Servizio Marconi) che attua un'azione di facilitazione ed accompagnamento a questa attività. Maggiori informazioni al link: <https://bit.ly/EuroSmoooc21>.*

Note to teachers from Ireland: *It may be possible to count the completion of this course as part fulfilment of any discretionary CPD hours, subject to your school management's approval. Therefore, please enquire with your school management if your participation in this course can be formally recognised.*

Course Staff

Júlia Lotina Cartanyà - Course Coordinator

Júlia is a Project Coordinator at the Science Education Department of European Schoolnet (EUN), a network of over 30 Ministries of Education based in Brussels. Júlia coordinates the Smart Connected Classrooms pilot project and Carbon Act, as well as EUN's contributions to CROPS. She has supported the coordination the Exploring Nature-Based Solutions in Your Classroom MOOC (Rerun) and developed and coordinated the Bring the Ocean into Your School and Carbon Act: Innovative Teaching for Climate Solutions MOOCs. Júlia holds a master's degree in Social Policy, specialising in education.

Anita Šimac - Course Moderator

Anita is a passionate mathematics teacher and mentor at Petra Preradovića Elementary and Lower Secondary School in Zadar, Croatia. As the head of the county expert council for mathematics teachers, she promotes collaboration and lifelong learning among educators. Since 2016, she has been a Scientix ambassador and a member of the Microsoft Innovative Educator Expert community, using digital tools to engage and inspire her

students. Anita is also a dedicated eTwinning ambassador, known for her award-winning contributions and leadership in both national and international STEM projects. Her teaching philosophy is rooted in project-based learning, where mathematics becomes a gateway to curiosity, creativity, and scientific exploration. Whether linking mathematics with art, sustainability, or real-life challenges, Anita empowers her students to see learning as an adventure. Her innovative approach continues to influence peers and pupils alike, shaping a more dynamic and connected future for education across Europe.

Behind the Course

[CROPS](#) is an EU-funded Horizon Europe project that will help citizen science projects grow and have a greater impact across Europe. The project will identify citizen science initiatives with the potential to expand their impact across the 5 EU Missions – Climate Change Adaptation; Cancer; Healthy Oceans and Seas; Climate-Neutral and

Smart Cities; and Soil Health – and develop practical tools, protocols, and strategies to support the expansion of these initiatives. By connecting research with society, CROPS aims to tackle major challenges and contribute to Horizon Europe’s vision of open, impactful innovation.

[Scientix®](#), the community for science education in Europe, promotes and supports a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other STEM education professionals.

Disclaimer

Funded by
the European Union

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1 Module 1: Introduction to Citizen Science and the Five EU Missions

1.1 Module Introduction

1.1.1 Welcome to the CROPS MOOC!

Welcome to the “From Classroom to Impact: Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science” course!

We’re excited to have you here! This course is designed especially for educators like you – curious, committed, and ready to make a difference.

Together, we will explore how citizen science can become a powerful tool in your classroom.

In the upcoming modules, you will:

- ✓ Learn what citizen science is and how it helps solve real-world problems.
- ✓ Identify inspiring citizen science projects you can easily bring into your lessons.
- ✓ Explore how to turn these projects into meaningful learning experiences for your students.

But that’s not all!

You’ll also connect with a vibrant community of teachers, educators, and science enthusiasts who share your passion for learning and creating real-world impact.

 Let’s start here our journey – from classroom to impact!

Are you ready? Let’s go!

1.1.2 Overview of course content

This MOOC is structured into four exciting modules.

By the end of the course, you’ll create your very own **Citizen Science learning scenario**, inspired by everything you’ve learned – and ready to use in your teaching!

Here’s what’s coming up:

Module 1: Introduction To Citizen Science and The Five EU Missions (opening on 13/10/2025)

We'll kick off with the basics of citizen science – what it is, why it matters, and how it connects to the five EU Missions on oceans, smart cities, cancer, climate and soil.

Module 2: Choosing The Right Citizen Science Project For Your Students (opening on 20/10/2025)

Module 2 presents a variety of citizen science projects and guides you in selecting those that best suit your classroom needs.

Module 3: Planning and Implementing Citizen Science Activities (opening on 27/10/2025)

Module 3 introduces five example learning scenarios – one for each EU Mission – and supports you in designing learning activities around citizen science projects.

Module 4: Assessing Students' Learning and Impact Of Citizen Science Projects (opening 03/11/2025)

Module 4 invites you to apply what you've learned throughout the course. You'll design and submit your learning scenario, with support and feedback from your course peers.

1.1.3 Course live events

[Don't miss our live events!](#)

In Module 1 (this week!), on **Wednesday, 15 October (17:00 – 18:00 CEST)**, join us to hear directly from our CROPS Citizen Science Champions. They'll share real stories of citizen science projects that have made a real impact across Europe. It's a great chance to see citizen science in action!

Then, in Module 4, on **Thursday 06 November (17:00 – 18:00 CET)**, join our TeachMeet – a friendly space to present your early ideas for your CROPS learning scenario or to showcase any citizen science activities you've run with your students. Let's connect, learn from each other, and spark new inspiration!

Can't make it live? No worries!

All sessions will be recorded and available anytime on the MOOC platform under the [Live Events section](#).

We can't wait to see you there!

1.1.4 Welcome to Module 1!

“... citizen science offers the power of science to everyone, and the power of everyone to science.”

Jennifer Shirk (Executive Direction, Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences)

Welcome to this foundational module, created to provide you with a solid understanding of citizen science – an exciting way to connect your students with real-world scientific discovery.

By the end of this module, you'll be able to:

- ✓ Describe the core ideas of citizen science, including its main principles and why it's important in today's society.
- ✓ Explain the advantages of using citizen science in your teaching.
- ✓ Identify the five EU Missions and explain how citizen science can help achieve their objectives.
- ✓ Locate and effectively use online citizen science platforms to find, join, and contribute to relevant projects.
- ✓ Use the CROPS learning scenario template.

Get ready to bring citizen science alive in your classroom. Your journey starts here!

1.1.5 Note from the course instructors

Before we begin this exciting journey, we'd like to share two quick notes with you:

A note on using AI:

In this module, you'll take part in activities like Padlets, Tricider, and Discussion Forums, where you can share your ideas and experiences. These are meant to help you think more deeply about the course topics and connect with others. We encourage you to complete them on your own – without AI tools – to keep the conversations real and meaningful. If you need help, your fellow participants are just a post away 😊.

A note on course content and workload:

Module 1 includes a bit more content than the others, as it's meant to give you a solid foundation for the rest of the course. Don't worry – each module

will get lighter, giving you more time to focus on the final assignment as you progress.

We're glad to have you with us – let's get started!

1.2 Behind the MOOC

This MOOC has been developed by the CROPS project and is supported by Scientix®.

What is CROPS?

CROPS stands for **C**urating, **R**eplicating, **O**rchestrating, and **P**ropagating Citizen Science across Europe.

It's a Horizon Europe-funded project that helps citizen science initiatives grow and have greater impact across Europe – especially by connecting them with the goals of the five important [EU Missions](#):

 Climate Change Adaptation

 Cancer

 Oceans & Waters

 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

 Soil Health

Why CROPS?

Citizen science has huge potential – but many initiatives stay local or small-scale. CROPS supports these projects to grow by identifying what works, providing tools and strategies, and building strong communities around shared societal goals.

Why this MOOC?

The education community has great potential to amplify the impact of citizen science initiatives. This MOOC helps educators like you connect with citizen science projects, supporting CROPS' goal to engage more people and create a bigger impact together.

Who's behind CROPS?

CROPS is led by a team of six expert organisations:

[INOVA+](#)

[Earthwatch Europe](#)

[International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis](#)

[Ideas for Change](#)

[OutBe](#)

[European Schoolnet](#)

Want to know more?

Visit the CROPS [website](#) or follow us on [Bluesky](#), [IG](#), [Facebook](#), [TikTok](#), or [LinkedIn](#).

About Scientix

[Scientix®](#), the community for science education in Europe, promotes and supports a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other STEM education professionals.

1.2.1 Welcome from your course team

Before we get started, [here's a short video message from our MOOC moderator](#), Anita Šimac, to welcome you to the course!

1.2.2 Activity: Meet your peers!

But now, we want to know more about you!

Jump into the Padlet below and share a quick introduction:

- Where are you from?
- What do you do? (Teacher, teacher trainer, student teacher, researcher?)
- Why did you join this course, and what do you hope to gain?
- Do you have any previous experience in citizen science?

Then, keep the conversation going! Reply to at least two fellow participants with a warm welcome or a question to spark a chat.

And don't forget to join our [CROPS MOOC Facebook group](#) – connect, share ideas, and keep the learning alive even after the course!

you couldn't answer right away, or maybe it sparked a sense of curiosity or concern.

Chances are, yes!

Think about a time when that happened. Maybe it was something unusual in a park, your garden, or even on your daily walk. In that moment, you might have asked yourself:

- Why is this happening?
- Is it a good thing, or should I be worried?
- Can I do anything about it?

Here's an example:

Imagine it's the middle of summer and you're out for an evening walk after a hot day. You pass by a pond or a small lake in your local park – but something looks off. The water is covered in a thick green layer. It smells kind of bad, too. You wonder, *What is that? Is it pollution? Could it be harmful to wildlife, or even to people?*

You've just made a scientific observation! That green layer could be algae – sometimes harmless, sometimes a warning sign of pollution or rising temperatures.

Now, take a look at the image below. What do you notice?

Image licensed from Adobe Stock / © Patrycja

- What colour is the water?
- Are there signs of wildlife?
- Do you see trash, nearby lawns, or anything unusual?

You've probably spotted things in the picture that caught your attention – maybe the colour of the water, the absence of wildlife, or rubbish along the edge.

These kinds of everyday observations can contribute to something bigger.

That's where citizen science comes in.

Citizen science involves people – like you – helping to collect and share observations that contribute to real scientific research. In the example provided, it might mean joining a local water monitoring project or submitting what you see through an app or website.

On their own, individual observations may seem small. But when combined with data from others, they can help scientists and decision-makers track pollution, detect harmful algal blooms, and better understand how the environment is changing.

Your curiosity matters – and what you notice can help make a real difference!

1.3.3 What is citizen science?

Citizen science is defined as:

“scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions”.

(Oxford English Dictionary)

In essence, citizen science is a way for people to get involved in research on topics they care about. Most of the time, it's voluntary and unpaid – people take part because they want to learn, contribute to science, or make a difference in their communities.

There are many types of citizen science projects. For example, you might classify galaxies with projects like [Galaxy Zoo](#); measure water levels in rivers or lakes to monitor droughts and floods with [CrowdWater](#); count specific types of insects in your garden to help track local biodiversity through platforms such as [iNaturalist](#) or [Bugs Matter](#); or listen for and identify bird calls in your neighbourhood using apps like [BirdNET](#).

No matter the topic, citizen science helps researchers collect more data from more places – something that would be very difficult to achieve without community involvement.

Image by Frits Ahlefeldt, licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 4.0. Source: <https://fritsahlefeldt.com/portfolio/citizen-science/>

1.3.4 Activity: Who can participate in citizen science?

Who do you think can participate in citizen science?

- A. A scout troop of young children
- B. A retired person interested in astronomy
- C. A family planting trees in their neighbourhood
- D. A group of cyclists tracking pollution levels during their rides
- E. A group of scuba divers collecting data on coral reef health

1.3.5 Answer: Who can participate in citizen science?

The previous activity might seem like a trick question, because the short answer is: anyone can participate in citizen science! Citizen science is open to everyone, regardless of age, experience, or background.

1.3.6 How your interests could connect to citizen science

One of the great things about citizen science is how easily it connects to everyday activities. You don't need to wear a lab coat or be an expert – many people contribute to research simply by doing things they already enjoy.

Whether on land, in the water, or online, there are countless ways to contribute!

[Click on the images in this Genially to find out more!](#)

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1.3.7 Why citizen science matters today

In recent years, citizen science has grown rapidly. A mix of technological progress – from smartphones to easy-to-use apps and online platforms – and wider societal shifts like rising education levels and the open science movement have made it easier for people to take part.

More people are now empowered to take part in science – and the results are transformative.

[In this short Genially presentation](#), we show why citizen science matters and how it benefits science, society, and the people who get involved. The images below are taken from that Genially presentation.

Project funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This MOOC is also supported by Scientix, an initiative of European Schoolnet®.

WHY CITIZEN SCIENCE MATTERS TODAY

Let's go! →

BENEFITS FOR SOCIETY

- Raising Awareness & Scientific Literacy
- Driving Policy & Collective Action
- Building Trust in Science

Click on each interactive card to view the explanation!

← Continue →

BENEFITS FOR SOCIETY

- Citizen science can improve scientific literacy and increase awareness on important societal issues
- Data gathered by citizen scientists can inform decisions at local, national, and global levels — empowering communities to advocate for change and shape their futures
- Involving citizens in research makes science more transparent and inclusive, which can increase public trust and support for evidence-based decisions

Click on each interactive card to view the explanation!

← Continue →

BENEFITS FOR SCIENCE

Expanding Data Collection

Bringing Fresh Ideas

Bridging Science and Society

Click on each interactive card to view the explanation!

←
Continue
→

BENEFITS FOR SCIENCE

Citizen science enables researchers to gather data across broader geographic areas and longer time periods than would be possible otherwise

Participants contribute diverse perspectives and local knowledge, which can lead to new insights, better research questions, and more relevant outcomes

Public involvement helps align scientific research with real-world needs, making it more responsive and impactful

Click on each interactive card to view the explanation!

←
Continue
→

BENEFITS FOR PARTICIPANTS

Learning Through Doing

Empowerment and Civic Participation

Connection and Enjoyment

Click on each interactive card to view the explanation!

←
Return
→

Citizen science is already achieving impressive results worldwide. Next, you'll discover some of them!

1.3.8 Global citizen science success stories

Across the globe, everyday people are helping solve scientific mysteries, protect biodiversity, and even advance medical research. [This Genially shows how citizen scientists are making a difference.](#)

Image 1: DNA Molecule by pixabay.com. Under CC0 content Licence.

Gamers Crack a 10-Year Puzzle

Scientists had spent a decade trying to model a protein structure crucial to AIDS research. Then they tried something different: sharing the puzzle with players of the online game Foldit. In just **three weeks**, the players found the solution!

Source: Scientific American

← Next →

Powered by genially

Image 2: Galaxy by pixabay.com. Under CC0 content Licence.

Mapping the Universe — Galaxy Zoo

In July 2007, astronomers faced a huge challenge: **classifying 1 million galaxies** from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. Even if all the world's astronomers worked full-time, it would have taken **200 years to complete**. To tackle this, they launched Galaxy Zoo, a public citizen science project — and the results were remarkable. Within **24 hours**, volunteers were submitting **70,000 classifications** per hour. By the end of the first year, **150,000 people** had made over **50 million classifications**. Each galaxy was reviewed multiple times, improving data reliability and accuracy.

Source: California Academy of Sciences

← Next →

Powered by genially

Image 3: Ladybug by pixabay.com. Under CC0 content Licence.

The Lost Ladybug Returns

The nine-spotted ladybug (*Coccinella novemnotata*) is New York's state insect — but it hadn't been seen since **1982** and was believed extinct. That is, until a citizen scientist spotted it on a sunflower in Long Island in **2011**, as part of the Lost Ladybug Project. This single observation brought the species back into the spotlight!

Source: Wikipedia

← Next →

Powered by genially

Image 4: Industrial Chimneys by pexels.com. Under CC0 content Licence.

Cleaner Air in Tonawanda

In **2004**, residents of Tonawanda, New York, noticed worsening air quality and rising health issues. They formed the Clean Air Coalition, used low-cost air sensors, and discovered dangerously high benzene levels. Their data pushed state and federal agencies to act — and **benzene levels dropped by 86%**.

Source: [CitizenScience.gov](https://citizenscience.gov)

← **Next** →

Powered by

Image 5: Brain Photo by Robina Weermeijer on Unsplash. Licensed under the Unsplash License.

Helping Alzheimer's Research in a Weekend

In a **single weekend**, citizen scientists using the Stall Catchers platform analysed enough online videos to match **3.5 months of laboratory research** — all to support studies on Alzheimer's disease.

Source: [Science Connected Magazine](https://www.scienceconnectedmagazine.com)

← **Next** →

Powered by

Image 6: Bird Photo by Boris Smokrovic on Unsplash. Licensed under the Unsplash License.

Citizen Scientists Mapped Earth's 50 Billion Birds

Over **600,000 citizen scientists** contributed bird sighting data globally via eBird, enabling researchers to estimate **50 billion wild birds** across **9,700 species**.

Source: [ABC News](https://www.abcnews.com)

← **Previous** →

Powered by

These are just a few examples of the global impact of citizen science – next, you'll meet the CROPS Citizen Science Champions driving change across Europe!

1.3.9 CROPS citizen science champions

Want to hear their stories firsthand?

From classrooms to coastlines, gardens to smart cities, the CROPS podcast series takes you behind the scenes of Europe's most inspiring citizen science projects. Tune in to hear directly from the people making them happen!

All episodes are available on [Spotify](#) and [here!](#)

1.4 Getting Started: How to Get Involved in Citizen Science

1.4.1 Join the movement!

Now that you've seen the power of citizen science in action, are you excited to get involved yourself?

1.4.2 Citizen science: Different ways to get involved

In the previous section, we learned that citizen science projects bring together two main groups: scientists, who usually initiate and guide the

research, and members of the public who participate as volunteer citizen scientists.

But not all citizen science projects work the same way!

Experts have identified different ways that citizens and scientists collaborate. According to studies by [Bonney et al. \(2009\)](#) and [Follett and Strezov \(2015\)](#), these projects generally fall into three main types:

CONTRIBUTORY (Providing data to a researcher's project)	COLLABORATIVE (Working with researchers to determine how data will be collected and used)	CO-CREATED (Working with researchers throughout every stage of the project)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Collect samples •Analyse samples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Develop explanations •Design data collection methods •Collect samples •Analyse samples •Analyse data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Define a question or issue •Gather information •Develop explanations •Design data collection methods •Collect samples •Analyse samples •Analyse data •Interpret data and make conclusions •Disseminate conclusions •Discuss results and inquire further

As you can see, there are many ways to get involved in citizen science, no matter your available time, skills, or interests.

Whether you want to contribute a little or get fully involved, there's a place for you!

1.4.3 Activity: Match citizen science models with their definitions and examples

Another well-known classification of citizen science projects based on participant engagement is the one developed by [Haklay \(2013\)](#).

Can you match each citizen science model with the correct definition and a real-life example?

Just drag and drop the right items into place!

TERM	DEFINITION	EXAMPLE
Crowdsourcing	People contribute time or use of their devices (e.g. smartphones or computers). The cognitive engagement is minimal.	Using your phone to measure noise or air quality while walking around the city.
Distributed intelligence	People help process large amounts of research material. They might sort through data, interpret simple findings, or help categorise information.	Online volunteers tagging animal species in camera trap photos.
Participatory science	People are involved from the beginning of the project. They take part in defining the research question, collecting data, and assisting with analysis. Still, the researcher or expert has a high level of control over the analysis and interpretation.	Taking part in a local park's bird count, where you learn to identify species and follow set protocols to record sightings for studies led by ornithologists.
Extreme citizen science	Researchers and volunteers develop the various steps in the research process together. But here the role of the scientist is confined to that of facilitator. The volunteers run the citizen science project and do the work.	A community group creates a water quality monitoring program for a local lake after noticing fish deaths. They select sites, collect and analyse samples, and use the data to suggest solutions to local authorities.

Did you manage? It wasn't an easy task!

1.4.4 Ten principles of citizen science

By now, you've seen that citizen science can take many shapes — so it's no surprise that defining it isn't always straightforward. In fact, having just one definition can be risky: it might leave out valuable activities or limit how certain projects are recognised in scientific fields.

What unites all citizen science is one key feature: public participation in scientific research.

To help provide clarity and guidance, the [European Citizen Science Association \(ECSA\)](#) published the Ten Principles of Citizen Science in 2015. These principles outline what good citizen science looks like – from how data should be handled and shared, to ethical considerations, and the roles of participants and scientists.

You can find the Ten Principles of Citizen Science translated into 41 languages [here!](#)

1.4.5 Where to find citizen science projects?

Now that you've learned what citizen science is and how it works, you might be wondering: *Where can I actually get involved?*

Great news – there are many platforms and organisations that connect volunteers with real scientific research!

Here are a few popular platforms where you can browse and join citizen science projects from around the world:

- [Zooniverse](#): A large online platform with hundreds of projects across disciplines – from astronomy to history. Many are beginner-friendly and can be done from home.
- [SciStarter](#): A U.S.-based platform that hosts a wide range of projects. You can filter by location, topic, or activity type to find one that suits you.
- [European Citizen Science Platform](#): A European hub that offers projects, resources, and tools to support citizen science across the continent.
- [iNaturalist](#): A global community where you can share nature observations and help scientists monitor biodiversity.
- [ScienceUs](#): A Europe-wide initiative that helps citizen science projects grow and connect with broader networks.

You can also find citizen science opportunities through:

- Universities and research institutions
- Museums and science centres

- Environmental and educational NGOs
- Local community organisations
- National or regional science education networks

These groups often run citizen science projects directly or can help you connect with ones that match your interests or your learners' needs.

 Tip: Keep an eye on newsletters or social media pages of these organisations – they often post open calls for participants!

1.4.6 Activity: Mapping citizen science around you

Citizen science is often closer than we think – universities, museums, NGOs, schools, and even local governments are running or supporting projects that invite public participation in science.

In this activity, we encourage you to add a pin to the location of an organisation you know that is involved in citizen science.

[Let's build this map together and see how wide the citizen science network truly reaches!](#)

1.4.7 Halfway through module 1

You're halfway through the first module – well done!

Before moving on or taking a break, here's a quick quiz to see what you've picked up about citizen science so far 😊.

1.4.8 Activity: Citizen science quiz – test your knowledge!

1. What is the key feature that defines citizen science?

- A) Scientific research restricted to academic settings
- B) Public participation in scientific research
- C) Scientific research only conducted by citizens
- D) Scientific research conducted in public spaces

2. Which of the following activities would NOT be considered citizen science?

- A) Watching birds in your backyard and submitting sightings to a biodiversity database
- B) Taking photos of flowers and uploading them to a nature observation app like iNaturalist

- C) Signing an online petition to protect endangered species
- D) Using a smartphone app to record local air quality measurements during your walk

3. What is the term for citizen science projects where volunteers help classify or categorize large amounts of data online, like tagging animal species in photos?

- A) Online monitoring
- B) Distributed intelligence
- C) Community-based observation
- D) Extreme citizen science

4. Which of these is NOT a benefit of citizen science for society?

- A) Raising awareness on important societal issues
- B) Empowering communities to advocate for change
- C) Eliminating the need for professional scientists
- D) Building public trust in science

5. In which project did volunteers classify over 50 million galaxies within a year?

- A) Galaxy Zoo
- B) Galaxy Tracker
- C) Universe Watch
- D) AstroScope

1.5 Citizen Science and Education

1.5.1 Welcome back!

We hope you enjoyed the quiz and feel confident about your understanding of citizen science so far!

In the first half of Module 1, we covered the core definition(s) of citizen science, explored the diverse ways everyday people can get involved, discussed its benefits for science, society, and participants, and even celebrated some inspiring global success stories. You also learned where to find projects and about the guiding principles from organisations like ECSA.

However, you might have been left wondering: ***What is my role as an educator in all of this, and why should I get my students involved in citizen science?***

Now, let's turn our attention to these important questions!

1.5.2 Activity: Have you ever participated in a citizen science project with your students?

But first, we have a question for you!

Have you ever participated in a citizen science project with your students?

Answers gathered from **378** respondents.

1.5.3 Activity: Share your experience!

Share your experience!

If you answered "yes" in the previous poll, [share in the Padlet below](#):

1. Which citizen science project did you and your students take part in?
2. How were you involved? Every story helps inspire others!

1.5.4 Activity: Why engage students in citizen science?

Now that we've explored the basics of citizen science and seen some great examples from fellow MOOC participants, it's time to address a key question:

Why do YOU think engaging students in citizen science is important? (Or maybe... what brought you to this MOOC? 😊)

[Share your thoughts on Tricider below!](#)

We've added a few starter ideas to help spark the conversation, but feel free to:

- ✓ Add your own ideas
- 👍 Vote for the ones you agree the most with
- 💡 Build on others' points
- ⚖️ Challenge or support ideas with arguments “for” or “against”

Bringing citizen science into the classroom can...

Boost scientific curiosity.
Encourage critical thinking.
Connect science to daily life.
Support inquiry-based learning.
Develop STEM and data literacy skills.
Build confidence and a scientific identity.
Provide authentic learning experiences.
Promote responsible citizenship.
Improve motivation and interest in learning science.
Support cross-disciplinary learning.

1.5.5 Meet the CROPS teachers!

Certainly, citizen science offers powerful opportunities to engage students in authentic, hands-on learning – and many teachers are already making it happen in their classrooms!

[In this video](#), you'll hear directly from five educators and citizen science champions who participated in the CROPS project.

 Watch the video to meet the CROPS teachers and hear what they said!

1.6 Citizen Science and the Five EU Missions

As you might recall from the beginning of this module, the CROPS project is all about helping citizen science projects make a real impact – especially in relation to the five key EU Missions.

But what exactly are these Missions, and why do they matter?

The EU Missions are ambitious initiatives designed to tackle some of the biggest challenges we face today. They focus on five areas: Climate Change Adaptation, Cancer, Oceans & Waters, Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, and Soil Health. Each mission sets clear goals to be achieved by 2030, aiming to improve lives and build a greener, healthier, and more resilient Europe.

Citizen science can contribute in meaningful ways – from local data collection to raising awareness and engaging communities.

As an educator, you can help students connect their learning to these big-picture goals – and show them that their contributions matter!

Next, you'll explore how each mission works and where citizen science fits in!

1.6.1 Adaptation to climate change

Climate change is already having a real impact on communities across Europe. The [Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change](#) aims to help at least **150 regions and communities** become more climate resilient by 2030. It supports local efforts to better understand climate risks and put practical solutions in place.

Whether it's extreme heat, floods, or changing weather patterns, we need to prepare for what's coming. This mission is about helping communities plan ahead, protect people and nature, and adapt how we live and work in the face of a changing climate.

How you can contribute through citizen science

Have you ever noticed changes in your local weather or environment – like more frequent heatwaves, heavier rainfall, or plants blooming earlier than usual? These everyday observations are valuable. By sharing them, you can help scientists and communities better understand how climate change is affecting your area and support the development of practical, locally targeted solutions.

If you'd like to learn more about this mission, [watch this short video](#):

1.6.2 Cancer

Cancer affects millions of people in Europe every year. The [EU Mission on Cancer](#) wants to improve the lives of **over 3 million people by 2030**, through better prevention, earlier diagnosis, more effective treatments, and improved support for patients.

How you can contribute through citizen science

Citizen science can play a role in raising awareness, promoting healthy habits, and gathering data to support prevention efforts. In schools, students can get involved in campaigns, health surveys, or projects that encourage their communities to adopt healthier lifestyles and learn about early detection.

If you'd like to learn more about this mission, [watch this short video](#):

1.6.3 Restore our oceans and waters

Our oceans and waters are the lifeblood of our planet – essential for people, nature, and the climate. But they're under serious pressure from pollution, overuse, and the growing impacts of climate change. The [EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”](#) aims to reverse this trend by 2030, with a clear goal: to restore the health of Europe’s marine and freshwater ecosystems.

To do this, the mission supports regional “lighthouses” – areas where innovative solutions are tested, demonstrated, and shared, helping communities across Europe take action and learn from each other.

How you can contribute through citizen science

You don't need a research vessel to contribute to this mission. Simple actions like helping with a local beach clean-up, reporting pollution you spot, or even just keeping an eye on local aquatic life, can provide key data. These kinds of observations help keep track of the health of our waters

and encourage a shared sense of care and responsibility for protecting them.

If you'd like to learn more about this mission, watch this short video:

1.6.4 Climate-neutral and smart cities

Cities are at the heart of Europe's climate goals. They may only cover **4% of land**, but they house **75% of the population**, use most of the energy, and produce over **70% of emissions**. The [Cities Mission](#) supports 100 cities in becoming climate-neutral by 2030 – and aims to inspire others to follow.

It's not just about clean energy or electric buses. The mission focuses on rethinking how cities function – reducing emissions while improving quality of life, with cleaner air, better transport, and greener spaces.

 How you can contribute through citizen science

Urban areas offer many opportunities for citizen-led data collection. Students and teachers can get involved in projects tracking air quality,

noise levels, or traffic patterns – or even helping map out greener routes for walking and cycling.

If you'd like to learn more about this mission, watch this short video:

1.6.5 Soil

We often overlook soil, but healthy soil is absolutely fundamental to everything – our food, clean water, biodiversity, even climate resilience. Yet, an estimated **60 to 70% of EU soils are in poor condition**. The [Soil Mission](#) aims to turn this around by 2030, with **100 living labs and lighthouse sites** leading the way toward healthier soils.

These labs bring together researchers, farmers, planners, and citizens to test solutions in real-life conditions – from farms to parks. They explore how to manage soil sustainably, restore damaged land, and help people better understand its value.

 How you can contribute through citizen science

Soil health might sound complex, but it's something students can explore in simple, meaningful ways. From testing soil in a school garden to observing land use changes in their neighbourhood, these everyday activities build awareness and help gather valuable data to protect this important resource.

If you'd like to learn more about this mission, watch this short video:

1.6.6 Activity: Connecting local challenges to EU missions through citizen science

You've just explored five important EU Missions, each aimed at tackling some of the most pressing challenges of our time – from climate change and soil health to cancer, oceans and our cities. **But these aren't just distant policy goals. They're connected to real issues in our communities, schools, and everyday lives.**

Citizen science projects have immense potential to drive progress towards EU missions. In this activity, we invite you to identify one project that will allow you and your students to connect with and contribute to one selected EU Mission.

 Here's how to get started:

Step 1: Spot a local challenge or opportunity.

Think about your school, your neighbourhood, or your wider community. What's something that needs improvement? What could be an opportunity to involve your students in making a difference?

Step 2: Link it to one of the five EU Missions.

Which of the five missions best matches the challenge you identified? Is it connected to climate adaptation, urban life, health, soil, or our waters?

Step 3: Bring citizen science in.

How can citizen science help solve this issue? What project could you join to make a difference?

Step 4: Find a fitting project.

Visit one of the platforms introduced earlier ([Zooniverse](#), [SciStarter](#), [EU-Citizen Science](#), or [iNaturalist](#)). Explore the projects listed and find one that relates to your chosen challenge or theme.

Step 5: [Share your match on the Padlet.](#)

Choose the correct EU Mission column. Post a short entry describing:

- The local challenge or opportunity you're focusing on.
- The citizen science project you selected.
- How your students could contribute to this project and the selected EU mission.

Please note: Posts that are entirely generated by AI and do not contribute meaningfully to the course discussion or exchange will be removed.

1.7 Final Assignment: The CROPS Learning Scenario Template (Step 1)

1.7.1 Introduction to the final course activity

To complete this course and receive your certificate in citizen science education, you need to successfully complete the **final course activity**.

Here's what it involves:

- **Create your own learning scenario** based on a citizen science project of your choice (linked to one of the five EU Missions).
- **Review and provide feedback** on three learning scenarios created by fellow participants.

You will build your learning scenario step by step throughout the MOOC, adding new sections in each module, as you go through new content. You'll need to submit the final version by **Wednesday, 19 November, 23:59 CET**.

This assignment is designed to help you put everything you've learned into practice and create a concrete plan you can use with your students.

And one more reason to give it your best: in **February 2026**, you'll have the chance to present your learning scenario in the [2026 STEM Discovery Campaign](#) – sharing your work beyond this course and inspiring teachers across Europe to bring citizen science into their classrooms.

1.7.2 CROPS learning scenario template

You can access [the CROPS learning scenario template](#) below. Each part of the template includes a short explanation to help you understand what to include.

But no need to worry just yet – we'll guide you through each section as the course continues. If you have any questions or need support along the way, you can always post them in the “Learning Scenario” discussion forum.

1.7.3 Introduction to process-oriented assessment (POA)

You will notice that the learning scenario template includes a section called *Reflect on your Development Process*. What does this mean? It means we're interested not only in your final product, but also in the steps you took to get there.

This focus on process applies not just to the final assignment, but to the whole MOOC. The course follows a **process-oriented approach to assessment**, where the design and development journey is valued just as much as the outcome. That's why you'll often encounter reflection questions inviting you to think about what you've learned and how you've learned it.

Throughout the modules, we will highlight the importance of your **learning journey** – how you plan, handle challenges, and adapt your approach – not just the end result. In today's era of AI, this is especially important: assessment should go beyond the final product and focus on the critical thinking process behind it. By reflecting on your process, you'll also support your own deeper learning, identifying both your strengths and the areas where you can continue to improve.

So as you work through the MOOC, we encourage you to reflect on *how* you are carrying out your tasks, not only on the results you achieve. To support you in this, you'll find short polls and reflection questions scattered throughout the course.

1.7.4 Learning Scenario peer-assessment rubric

As part of the final course activity, you are also asked to **review and provide feedback on three learning scenarios created by your fellow MOOC participants**.

Peer review is not just about helping others – it's a powerful way to reflect on your own work, discover new ideas, and strengthen the quality of your learning scenario.

To make this process clear and fair, we've prepared a [peer-assessment rubric](#). This tool sets out the criteria for evaluating each section of a learning scenario and will help you give constructive, focused feedback. At the same time, it will also guide you in improving your own work by showing you what reviewers will be looking for.

Think of the rubric not only as an assessment tool, but also as a **practical checklist** you can use while drafting and refining your own scenario.

[You can download the rubric here.](#)

1.7.5 Activity: Designing a strong learning scenario

You've just explored the rubric that will help us build and refine truly impactful citizen science learning scenarios!

In this activity, you are invited to share your ideas and opinions about the proposed rubric for self- and peer- assessment.

Your feedback might be used to clarify and/or refine the rubric, ensuring it meets the needs of the group. Feel free to engage with others' comments, like posts, and collaborate with your peers on this course's rubric. Let's start!

Questions [added to the Padlet](#):

- Look at the main categories in the rubric. Do they cover all the different dimensions of a successful citizen science learning scenario? Is anything missing?
- The rubric uses labels (e.g., 'Excellent', 'Moderate', 'Low', 'Absent'). Do these labels clearly convey the different levels of achievement?

- For each category, there's a description explaining what it means. Are these descriptions clear and easy to follow? Do they help you know what to look for?

1.8 Additional Resources on Citizen Science

1.8.1 Do you want to learn more?

Before we finish Module 1, here are some valuable resources if you want to explore citizen science further. These include useful guides, courses, videos, and online communities that can inspire and support you on your citizen science journey.

Publications

[Citizen Science for All: A Guide for Citizen Science Practitioners](#): This guide offers practical advice and best practices for anyone involved in running or participating in citizen science projects.

[White Paper on Citizen Science for Europe](#): This document outlines the strategic importance of citizen science for Europe, discussing its potential and challenges within a policy context.

[EUTOPIA's Citizen Science Starter Kit](#): This kit provides essential tools and introductory information for individuals or groups looking to initiate their first citizen science project.

Online Courses

[Foundations of Citizen Science by SciStarter](#): This course provides a comprehensive introduction to the fundamental principles and practices of citizen science, ideal for beginners.

Videos

[Citizen Science: An Introduction Video](#): This video gives an overview of different aspects of citizen science, such as communication, data quality and inclusiveness.

[Citizen Science: Everybody Counts](#): This video emphasizes the inclusive nature of citizen science, highlighting how anyone can contribute to scientific research.

[What is Citizen Science?](#): This video offers a concise definition and overview of what citizen science entails, explaining its core concepts.

[The Awesome Power of Citizen Science:](#) This video showcases the significant impact and broad potential of citizen science in addressing real-world scientific questions and societal challenges.

Citizen Science & EU Missions

[CROPS Transnational Community Online Spaces:](#) This online space fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange among people working on citizen science projects related to the EU Missions.

1.9 Webinar Announcement

1.9.1 Webinar: Scientix® & CROPS Webinar: Meet The CROPS Citizen Science Champions – Stories of Impact in Citizen Science

Date: Wednesday, 15 October, 17:00 CET

Recording

Webinar: Scientix® & CROPS Webinar: Meet The CROPS Citizen Science Champions

Unlisted

[You can download the presentation here.](#)

Behind every citizen science project is a story worth telling.

In this webinar, you'll meet the passionate individuals behind some of Europe's most exciting citizen science initiatives. From monitoring traffic and exploring soil biodiversity to studying women's health, sailing for ocean

data, or mapping invasive species, these project leaders will share how they engage citizens – young and old – in hands-on science that truly matters.

You'll hear how their projects got started, the impact they're having, and how they connect science with schools, communities, and policy. This is a unique chance for teachers and the wider citizen science community to go "behind the scenes" and get inspired by real-life citizen science success stories.

EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change

Sofie Meeus is a research scientist at Meise Botanic Garden in Belgium, working on citizen science, biodiversity informatics, and ecological outreach. She holds a Ph.D. in Biological Sciences from the University of Leuven and has led public engagement projects like [#HOMEsafari](#), [KIKS](#), and several bioblitzes. Her review "[More than a Bit of Fun: The Multiple Outcomes of a Bioblitz](#)" was published in *Bioscience*. Sofie connects science and society through open data, collaborative research, and participatory biodiversity monitoring. She co-chairs the European Citizen Science Association's Green Spaces group and plays a key role in the [OneSTOP](#) project, focusing on the social and policy aspects of invasive species management.

EU Mission: Cancer

Leonore Vander Donck holds a master's degree in bioscience engineering and is currently pursuing a PhD at the University of Antwerp. Her research focuses on how menstrual products influence the vaginal microbiome, as part of the large-scale citizen science project [Isala](#) in Belgium. Isala is the largest citizen science study on the vaginal microbiome and won the **EU Grand Prize for Citizen Science in 2023**. The project has since expanded into a global framework, with daughter studies like the [Luna](#) project in Belgium, and sister projects in over 15 countries.

EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters

Arianna Liconti is a marine biologist and storyteller who bridges science, policy, and ocean communities. Born in Reggio Calabria, Italy, she holds a BSc in Marine Biology from Bangor University and an MRes in Marine Ecology and Conservation from Plymouth University. After early research at the Marine Biological Association UK, she returned to the Mediterranean and now leads projects like [CROPS](#), [CSMACH1](#), and [The Ocean Race](#), connecting scientists, sailors, and citizens to protect the sea. An experienced offshore sailor with over 18,000 nautical miles, Arianna lives full-time aboard her sailing boat *Binba*, working at the intersection of research, outreach, and adventure – with passion, dedication, and a deep love for the Ocean.

EU Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

Kris Vanherle is the co-founder of [Telraam](#), a company using affordable IoT devices to empower citizens to monitor traffic in their neighbourhoods. The project aims to bring together residents and local authorities in a collaborative process to understand data, identify mobility challenges, and co-create solutions for better urban planning.

Glenn Godin has worked as Project Manager for School Mobility & Parking Policy at [Mobiel 21](#) since 2020. With expertise in road safety and mobility management, he leads citizen participation projects, contributes to European initiatives focused on cycling and parking policy, and consults children of all ages to improve traffic safety in school environments.

EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe

Nadine Greenhalgh is Biodiversity Partnerships Manager at [Basecamp Research](#), a company working toward “better medicines, better food, and better products for the planet” by exploring the rich and largely unknown biodiversity in soil. Nadine has built partnerships in over 20 countries, accessing unique soil samples from communities worldwide. These collaborations help discover new proteins and enzymes found in soil – some of which are already being used by partners like [Protein Evolution](#) to break down plastic waste. Nadine’s work also ensures that the people and communities providing samples are treated fairly, receiving royalties, regular updates on how their samples are used, and support through the creation of local DNA sequencing labs.

1.9.2 Activity: Do you have any questions for our guest speakers?

Do you have any questions for our guest speakers? [Post them in the Padlet and we will address them during the webinar!](#)

1.9.3 Join our TeachMeet!

And that’s not all – we also have a **TeachMeet** coming up on **Thursday 6 November at 17:00 CET**.

A TeachMeet is a friendly, interactive event where teachers share short, practical presentations with peers. It’s a great chance to exchange ideas, get inspired, and showcase your own classroom experiences with citizen science.

Would you like to be one of our speakers? [Fill in this form to propose your contribution!](#)

Don’t worry – it can be as simple as:

- Sharing your learning scenario idea,
- Presenting an activity that worked well with your students, or
- Talking about your experience engaging students in citizen science.

Even if you don’t present, joining the TeachMeet is a wonderful way to connect with others in the MOOC community and take away fresh ideas for your own teaching.

So, save the date – and we look forward to seeing you there!

1.10 Module Round-Up

1.10.1 Summary

Great work! We have made it through Module 1 😊

- ✓ You can describe the core ideas and main principles of citizen science and understand why it's important today.
- ✓ You can explain the benefits of using citizen science in your teaching.
- ✓ You can identify the five EU Missions and understand how citizen science can help achieve their goals.
- ✓ You know how to find and use online citizen science platforms to join and contribute to projects.
- ✓ You're familiar with the CROPS learning scenario template and assessment rubric

See you next week – looking forward to continuing this citizen science journey with you!

2 Module 2: Choosing the Right Citizen Science Project for Your Students

"The most exciting phrase to hear in science, the one that heralds new discoveries, is not 'Eureka!' but 'That's funny...'"

Isaac Asimov

2.1 Welcome to Module 2!

In **Module 1**, you explored what citizen science is, including its types, guiding principles, and how it supports both student learning and broader EU mission goals. You also discovered where to find citizen science projects.

Now, in **Module 2**, we'll turn our focus to choosing the right project for your teaching context.

This module will help you:

- ✓ Apply key criteria to assess whether a citizen science project is a good fit for your students and curriculum.
- ✓ Plan the practical steps to successfully integrate a project into your teaching.
- ✓ Explore a variety of citizen science projects linked to the five EU Missions.
- ✓ Select a project that aligns with your educational goals, your students' skills, and the resources available to you.
- ✓ Begin developing your learning scenario.

Let's get started!

 Important notice:

In this module, you'll take part in activities like Padlets, Tricider, and Discussion Forums, where you can share your ideas and experiences. These are meant to help you think more deeply about the course topics and connect with others. We encourage you to complete them on your own – without AI tools – to keep the conversations real and meaningful. If you need help, your fellow participants are just a post away 😊

2.2 Questions to Address Before Engaging in a Citizen Science Project

2.2.1 Assessing the right fit

There are *many* citizen science projects out there, but not all are suitable for the classroom. Before involving your students, it's important to assess whether a project is a **good fit** for your specific teaching situation. Ask yourself: does this project align with my teaching goals? Does it match my students' age and skill levels? Can it be done with the time and resources we have?

In this part of the module, we will walk through the **key factors** to consider when selecting a project. This will help ensure the project you choose is both **meaningful** for student learning and **practical** in your teaching context.

By the end of this section, you'll have a checklist of criteria to **evaluate any citizen science project's fit** for your class.

Next, you'll dive into each question one by one!

2.2.2 Activity: Your top 3 factors

But before we dive in – let's start with a quick warm-up!

What do you consider essential when choosing a citizen science project for your class?

Enter up to three words or short phrases that highlight what you think matters most!

Does this project help me meet my curriculum goals?

A project might be fascinating, but if it doesn't reinforce your curriculum or learning goals, it may not be the best use of classroom time.

To help you assess this, [this Genially outlines four key steps to consider](#).

A Genially interactive slide with a purple background and a light blue navigation bar at the top containing a home icon and numbers 1 through 4. The main title is "MATCHING CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS TO CURRICULUM, SKILLS & STUDENTS' INTERESTS". Below the title, it says "Explore the four steps by clicking each number — a simple guide to aligning CS projects with your curriculum!". Logos for "crops" and "SCIENTIX" are on the left, and the European Union logo with a disclaimer is on the right. A "genially" watermark is in the bottom left corner.

A Genially interactive slide showing step 1. The navigation bar at the top has the number 1 highlighted. The main content area is dark blue with a large white number "1" on the left. The text reads: "Match the Project to Curriculum Standards. Start by reviewing your syllabus or curriculum framework. Identify the key concepts, topics, and skills that your students are expected to master. Look for citizen science projects that naturally support these areas." To the right, a light blue box titled "Examples" contains two paragraphs: "If your curriculum includes biodiversity, ecosystems, or species identification, a bird count, insect survey, or local nature observation project could directly reinforce those topics." and "If you teach about climate change, weather patterns, or seasonal changes, projects that monitor temperature, rainfall, or tree phenology (e.g., recording when trees flower or lose leaves) could be a perfect fit." A "genially" watermark is in the bottom left corner.

Home 1 2 3 4

2

Support Specific Learning Objectives

Next, think about the learning goals you want to achieve with your students. Beyond content knowledge, what **skills** or **competencies** are you trying to develop?

Ask yourself:

- Do I want students to practise **collecting and working with data**?
- Am I aiming to build **digital skills**, such as using apps, online tools, or data platforms?
- Should they learn how to **communicate scientific findings** effectively?

Citizen science projects offer many opportunities to practise these skills!

Presented by genially

Home 1 2 3 4

3

Consider Relevance and Student Interest

For students to stay engaged, the project should feel **relevant** and **meaningful**. One way to boost relevance is by connecting the project to local issues, current events, or topics students already care about.

Examples

If your school is near a river or coastline, students might be especially interested in a project about marine pollution or plastic waste.

If air quality is a local concern, students could gather and compare pollution data from different locations around town.

When students see a connection between the project and their lives or community, it meets both educational goals and personal relevance!

Presented by genially

Home 1 2 3 4

4

Step 4: Look for Cross-Curricular Opportunities

Many citizen science projects span multiple subject areas. These kinds of connections help students see how different subjects work together in the real world — and might even allow you to collaborate with colleagues from other subjects!

Example

A project about mapping local air quality can involve **science** (understanding pollution), **geography** (mapping data), **math** (interpreting sensor readings), and even **civics** (discussing public health).

Presented by genially

In short, a well-aligned project will reinforce your lessons rather than feeling like an add-on. This way, you can accomplish curriculum requirements *and* engage students in real scientific research at the same time. **It’s a win-win!**

2.2.5 Method Suitability: Is the project a good match for your students’ skills?

When selecting a citizen science project, it’s essential to ensure that the **activities and tasks are appropriate for your students’ age and skill level**. If a project is too simple, older students may quickly lose interest. If it’s too complex, younger students might feel overwhelmed or discouraged. In both cases, the learning experience suffers – and so can the **quality of the data** they contribute.

To help you select an age-appropriate project, we’ve outlined some general characteristics of different school levels and the types of methodologies that tend to work best:

Age group	Learner Profile	Best Fit Methodologies	Example Activities	Science Process Skills
Primary School (Ages 6–10)	Concrete thinkers who learn best through direct experience and hands-on tasks. Short attention spans, developing motor skills, high engagement with visual and tangible outcomes.	Simple observations, photo/drawing documentation, basic counting, exploring familiar environments, and quick-feedback tasks.	Identifying and recording plant growth stages, counting bird sightings in the schoolyard, drawing and labelling different cloud types, tallying types of litter on school grounds.	Observation, recording, simple classification.
Lower Secondary	Beginning to use abstract thinking, gaining	Structured data collection, use of basic tools,	Measuring water quality (e.g., pH, temperature	Measurement, pattern recognition,

Age group	Learner Profile	Best Fit Methodologies	Example Activities	Science Process Skills
Primary (Ages 11–14)	independence, improving digital and collaboration skills, motivated by real-world relevance and visible impact.	online data entry, teamwork, guided investigations, and trend analysis.), classifying wildlife images, collecting air quality data using simple sensors, tracking seasonal changes in local species.	basic data interpretation.
Upper Secondary (Ages 15–18)	Capable of abstract reasoning, independent inquiry, critical analysis, strong digital proficiency, and interest in ethical and societal issues.	Hypothesis-driven inquiry, complex data collection and analysis, use of digital visualisation tools, student-led investigations, community-focused projects, formal presentations.	Planning and conducting a biodiversity survey, analysing multi-week datasets, visualising trends using graphs or software, presenting environmental findings to the school or community.	Hypothesis testing, critical analysis, scientific communication.

*This table offers a general guide based on typical developmental stages. Keep in mind that student progress varies, and learning doesn't always follow a fixed path. The methodologies and skills listed are suggested focal points – not strict rules – and should be adapted to suit the needs, abilities, and context of your learners.

Remember, a well-chosen project should challenge your students just enough to promote learning, but not so much that they feel overwhelmed. It's about finding that sweet spot where students can participate confidently.

 Tip: If you're unsure where to start, begin with simpler activities to build their confidence and core skills. As they gain experience, you can

introduce more complex projects that deepen their scientific thinking and independence.

2.2.6 Knowledge Requirements: Are specific training or protocols required for successful data collection and participation?

Once you've found a project that matches your students' skills, the next step is making sure everyone knows *how* to do the tasks correctly.

Many citizen science projects include specific **protocols – clear steps that ensure data is collected in a consistent, reliable way**. These might be simple (like counting birds for 10 minutes in a 1x1 meter square) or more technical (like reading pH strips or using a rain gauge).

While assessing the citizen science project for classroom use, ask yourself:

- **Are the instructions clear and age-appropriate?** Make sure your students will understand what to do without getting confused or frustrated.
- **Will your students need a demo, practice round, or extra support?** Plan time to introduce tools or methods step by step, especially if they're new.
- **Are there training materials (videos, guides, quizzes) you can use in class?** Check the project website or platform – many offer ready-to-use resources you can build into your lesson.

Help your students understand that following the method carefully isn't just a rule – it's what makes their contributions useful to real scientists!

2.2.7 Activity: Designing age-appropriate science

Now let's put your knowledge into action!

In this activity, you'll explore **three** real citizen science projects that need some adjustments to work well for specific age groups. Each case study includes a challenge – something about the original design doesn't quite fit the students' abilities or needs.

Your task: identify what might be too difficult or confusing, and suggest simple, age-appropriate ways to adapt the project while still keeping it engaging and meaningful.

 For each case, write your thoughts in the text box provided. Once you submit, you'll see a set of possible solutions to compare with your own.

Let's start with the first case study!

Case Study 1: Sound Detectives	
Target Age Group	Primary students (ages 6–10)
Project Description	Students are asked to record environmental sounds in their local area (e.g., bird calls, traffic noise, wind) and upload the files to a citizen science platform for analysis by researchers studying soundscapes and biodiversity.
Challenge	This project wasn't originally designed with younger learners in mind. It involves tasks such as using audio recording equipment, uploading files independently, and logging time and location data — all of which may be too complex for primary-aged students
Your Task	What elements might be confusing or too advanced for this age group? How would you simplify or adapt the activity while still contributing useful sound data?
Possible Answer	<p>Some ideas to simplify or adapt the activity while still contributing useful sound data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher-led recording: Let the teacher manage uploads and details; students focus on choosing and recording sounds. • Use simple tools: Tablets or recorders with one-button functions work best. • Pre-fill details: Use forms or stickers for time/location info to keep data accurate. • Fewer, better uploads: Submit just one curated recording per class — quality over quantity. • Compare and describe sounds: Focus the activity on categorising sounds (e.g. loud/quiet, natural/human-made). • Make predictions: Involve students in guessing what sounds they might hear in different environments (e.g. forest vs. playground).

Let's now move on to the second case!

Case Study 2: Water Watchers		
Target Group	Age	Lower secondary students (ages 11–14)
Project Description	Participants collect water samples from local rivers or ponds and test for various indicators such as pH, nitrates, and turbidity using a portable water testing kit. They then submit their results through an online dashboard.	
Challenge	The project requires careful handling of test kits, accurate reading of chemical indicators, and understanding of what the results mean. Some students struggle with following multi-step protocols or interpreting ambiguous test strip colours, and data quality varies.	
Your Task	How could you adapt this project to make it more manageable for lower secondary students while maintaining valid data collection? What kind of scaffolding or support could you provide?	
Possible Answer	<p>Some ideas to adapt water testing activities for lower secondary students:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce the protocol: Let students practise first with safe substances (e.g. tap vs. bottled water). • Use visual aids: Provide colour charts or simple guides to help read test strips and follow procedures. • Simplify the dataset: Focus on 1–2 easy-to-measure indicators (e.g. pH and turbidity) to keep the task manageable. • Assign roles: Give each student a clear task (e.g. sampler, recorder, analyser). 	

Let's see now the third and final case!

Case Study 3: Classify the Cosmos		
Target Group	Age	Upper secondary students (ages 15–18)
Project Description	Students are asked to analyse and classify high-resolution telescope images of galaxies based on shape, brightness,	

	and other features. Their classifications contribute to a large astronomy database used by researchers.
Challenge	The activity is visually engaging, but the scientific concepts behind galaxy formation and classification are not fully explained. Some students treat the activity like a game and miss the deeper learning potential. Others lose interest without a clear sense of how their contributions fit into real research.
Your Task	How might you enrich this activity to make it more educational and relevant for older students?
Possible Answer	<p>Some ideas to improve learning in a galaxy classification project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set the scene: Briefly explain galaxy types, the universe’s structure, and how citizen science supports astronomy. • Encourage questions: Let students pose their own hypotheses (e.g. “Where do spiral galaxies appear most?”). • Use sample data: Have students present findings based on images they classified. • Add extras: Share short videos or visual tools to expand understanding. • Extend for advanced learners: Let them explore raw data or how AI supports galaxy analysis.

2.2.8 Required Equipment: What materials or tools are needed to participate?

Another key factor to consider when planning a citizen science project with your students is the **equipment required** to take part.

Citizen science projects can require anything from everyday objects to specialized scientific instruments. It’s vital to check the equipment and materials needed early on, so you can plan how to obtain them or find alternatives. Don’t worry – you don’t always need a high-end lab!

 Low-Cost Alternatives: If a project calls for specialised tools, don’t let that be a deal-breaker. Many educators find smart, low-cost workarounds. For example, if a professional water testing kit isn’t available, consider using simple paper test strips or building a basic thermometer from household materials. Need an air quality sensor? Look into budget-

friendly DIY kits or reach out to local science centres, libraries, or universities that may lend equipment. With a bit of creativity and planning, you can make high-quality participation possible – even without a big budget.

2.2.9 Activity: Gear up for citizen science!

Ready to test your science gear know-how?

Below are tools you'll often find in citizen science projects – from everyday items to more specialised equipment.

Drag each tool onto the task it best matches!

Take photos of species and upload them to a citizen science app.

Measure environmental indicators like pH, nitrates, and turbidity.

Record the precise location of sample collection in areas with limited connectivity.

Monitor local air conditions, such as particulate matter or CO₂ levels.

Capture environmental sounds for projects on biodiversity or noise pollution.

Record air or water temperature during sample collection or weather tracking.

Handle samples safely and prevent contamination.

Store collected samples (like water, soil, or leaves) for lab analysis.

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2.2.10 Time Requirements and Commitment: How will you integrate this project into the school schedule?

Time is a teacher's most valuable resource – so it's important to choose a citizen science project that fits realistically within your teaching timetable.

Projects can range from quick, one-off activities to long-term investigations that span weeks or months. Before jumping in, ask yourself: *How much time can I dedicate to this?*

Here are a few things to consider:

Short vs. long-Term: A one-day event like a Bioblitz might fit easily into a science week, while a semester-long monitoring project offers richer learning but needs sustained commitment. Align the project length with your goals and calendar – starting a six-month project right before exam season or school break might not be ideal.

Scheduling and frequency: Plan when and how often students will participate. Will it be a short daily task, a weekly session, or part of an after-school program? If the project requires regular observations, decide how to manage them during weekends or holidays – student rotations, catch-up days, or adjusted schedules can help.

Flexibility and backups: Build in a buffer for the unexpected – missed classes, bad weather, or tech issues. Have a Plan B ready: if you can't go outside, can students analyse previous data indoors? If a session is missed, can it be made up at home?

With a bit of upfront planning, even a busy schedule can accommodate a meaningful citizen science experience!

2.2.11 Legal and Ethical Requirements: Are there any data privacy or safety concerns regarding students' participation?

The last thing to think about – and one of the most important – is how to keep your students **safe, respectful, and protected** while taking part in citizen science.

Here are a few simple things to watch out for:

- **Protecting student data:** Some projects ask participants to upload data online or create accounts. Try to avoid using personal student details – a teacher-managed class account is often the easiest solution. And if students do need individual accounts, be sure to get parent or guardian permission. It's also a good idea to skim the

project's privacy policy so you know what's being collected and why. Keep in mind that some projects may also set minimum age requirements for participants.

- **Photos and locations:** If students are submitting photos or videos, make sure they don't include faces, names, or anything that could identify them – unless you've got permission.
- **Safety outside the classroom:** If your project takes students outdoors follow your school's normal safety steps. That means permission slips, enough adults to supervise, and a quick safety talk before heading out.
- **Kind and ethical science:** Citizen science is a great chance to talk about treating the environment with care. Encourage students to look, listen, and observe without disturbing animals or habitats. If they're collecting samples, make sure it's done responsibly and only if the project calls for it.
- **Being honest with data:** Sometimes students might feel pressure to record something "interesting." Remind them that in science, even a "nothing observed" result is valuable. What matters most is that the data is real and accurate.
- **Keep everyone in the loop:** Let parents and your school leadership know what you're doing – especially if the project involves online tools or going off-site.

Handling these details up front helps everything run smoothly and keeps the focus where it should be – on learning and discovery 😊.

2.2.12 Activity: Breaking down barriers in citizen science

As we've seen, choosing the right citizen science project for your students can feel like assembling a complex puzzle – there are many pieces (curriculum, time, equipment, protocols) and each project can present its own unique challenges.

We've explored the essential questions to ask, but now it's time to get real!

What are the actual hurdles you foresee when selecting a citizen science project for your students?

[Go to the Padlet and post:](#)

- **My Challenge (Red):** Think about a specific challenge *you* anticipate in selecting or implementing a citizen science project. Write it on a red sticky note on the board. For example, your challenge might be *“Fitting a project into our already packed semester”* or *“We have very limited equipment and budget”* or *“Not sure if my younger students will stay interested in long observations.”* Don’t be afraid to be honest – chances are someone else has the same concern!
- **Your Solution (Green):** Now, read through the challenges your peers have posted (the red notes). Pick one that you have a thought about, and add a green sticky note next to it offering a suggestion or solution.

Every challenge has a solution, or at least a way to mitigate it. And you’ve got a whole community here to help you find those solutions!

2.2.13 Selecting the right citizen science project for your students: Tips from CROPS teachers

But before we move into the next section, [let’s take a few minutes to hear what our CROPS teachers and citizen science champions have to say!](#)

2.3 Citizen Science Planning Worksheet

2.3.1 Planning your citizen science project

So far, we've looked at the key elements that go into choosing a citizen science project – and we've covered a lot of ground!

To help you pull it all together, we've created the [Citizen Science Planning Worksheet](#). Think of it as your step-by-step guide to choosing a project that truly works for *your* class – practical, manageable, and tailored to your teaching needs.

Use it to organise your ideas, reflect on key questions, and take the first steps from planning to action!

2.3.2 Activity: Evaluating citizen science projects

Over the last few sections, you've explored what makes a citizen science project a good fit for your classroom – from time and equipment needs to student engagement, safety, and curriculum alignment.

Now it's time to use those criteria to assess a real project!

Open this spreadsheet file containing 76 citizen science projects. Start by selecting the tab that matches your preferred EU Mission. Then, randomly choose **one project** to review.

👉 Please enter the name and code of the project you selected from the [Excel file](#) in the text box, following this format: **UK Soil Observatory / Soil02**

Name of the project:	
Code:	

Now that you've selected a project, let's take a closer look at whether it fits your teaching context.

✅ Project Fit Checklist

Go through the questions below and tick **Yes** or **No** based on the information available.

Some projects may not meet all the criteria – and that's perfectly fine! The goal is to reflect critically on how the project aligns with your classroom needs.

Remember, for this activity, you only need to complete the checklist for one project!

General Fit	
Is the project available in your region?	Yes / No
Is it free to access and use?	Yes / No
Is it available in a language your students understand?	Yes / No
Does it fit within your available teaching time?	Yes / No
Educational Suitability	
Does it align with your curriculum goals or subject content?	Yes / No
Is the content appropriate for your students' age group?	Yes / No
Are the tasks manageable for their skill and cognitive levels?	Yes / No
Training & Materials	
Are clear protocols or step-by-step instructions provided?	Yes / No
Are there teacher or student support materials (videos, guides, etc.)?	Yes / No
Equipment & Tools	
Is the required equipment easily accessible or affordable for your school?	Yes / No
Privacy & Safety	
Are safety or ethical guidelines clearly stated (especially for fieldwork)?	Yes / No
Are students' personal data protected?	Yes / No

2.3.3 Did you know?

The 76 projects you're exploring were selected from a pool of over **500 citizen science initiatives** reviewed by the CROPS team. Each one was assessed for its scalability and potential to contribute to the five EU Missions.

The overall methodology is described in [CROPS D2.1 – Scalability Assessment Framework](#) and criteria. A more detailed **Scalability Ranking Report (D2.2)** was also produced, but this document is not publicly available.

Next, you'll continue to the second half of this module – where you'll discover which projects from the list were identified as having the strongest potential to involve students!

But first, take a short break if you need it – you've earned it!

2.4 Citizen Science Project Examples

2.4.1 Introduction to citizen science project examples

Welcome to the second half of the module!

In the next units, you'll explore **17 citizen science projects** from the list provided in the previous activity, which we believe fulfil all the criteria and offer strong educational potential.

Each one is accompanied by a **Project Information Sheet** to help you quickly understand key details – such as how the project connects to your curriculum, what equipment is needed, or the suitable age group.

👉 Just a quick note: You don't need to go through all 17 projects! Focus on the ones linked to the mission(s) you're most interested in – or those you think would be a good fit for your students.

If a project stands out, feel free to explore it further on its website!

And as you go through them, you can already start thinking about whether any of these projects might be a good fit for your learning scenario! 😊

Let's explore the projects that are waiting for you!

2.5 Citizen Science Project Examples for the Climate Adaptation Mission

Let's begin with the first EU Mission: Climate Adaptation.

These projects invite students to step outdoors and become active researchers – tracking butterflies, birds, wildlife, and plants. They offer hands-on ways to explore biodiversity, understand environmental change, and contribute valuable data that supports nature conservation across Europe and beyond.

Ready to discover the projects?

2.5.1 European Butterfly Monitoring Scheme

Let's dive into our first citizen science project!

The [European Butterfly Monitoring Scheme \(EBMS\)](#) is a European project that tracks butterfly populations over time. Since butterflies are sensitive to changes in the environment, they're perfect indicators of how climate and habitats are changing. EBMS data has shown, for example, that **grassland butterflies have declined by 30% since 1990**.

[This sheet highlights the essential factors to keep in mind when involving your students in the project!](#)

Join the journey to protect Europe's butterflies!

2.5.2 eBird

Let's explore another great example of citizen science in action – this time through birds!

[eBird](#) is a global birdwatching project run by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology. Participants contribute observations of birds they see or hear, helping researchers study migration, population trends, and how birds respond to climate change and habitat loss.

[Explore the eBird project sheet here.](#)

Every bird counted makes a difference!

2.5.3 Observation.org

[Observation.org](#) gathers wildlife sightings from the public to help monitor biodiversity, track changes in species distribution, and inform nature conservation. The platform supports global data collection for everything from birds to insects, mammals, and plants – all verified by experts.

[In this project sheet](#), you'll find the basics for getting your students involved in eBird.

Observation.org makes it easy for students of all ages to explore nature and contribute valuable data, helping both their learning and global conservation efforts!

2.5.4 Budburst

[Budburst](#) is a project dedicated to tracking the timing of plant life cycle events, also known as **phenology**. It invites participants to observe and record key seasonal changes in plants, such as when buds open, leaves emerge, flowers bloom, and fruits ripen.

[Explore the Budburst project sheet here.](#)

Budburst wraps up our Climate Adaptation mission. Keep exploring to discover the exciting projects we've included for the other missions!

2.6 Citizen Science Project Examples for the Cancer Mission

Let's find out which project we've chosen for the Cancer mission!

2.6.1 Foldit

[Foldit](#) is a citizen science game that lets anyone become a virtual protein-folding expert. Players twist and fold 3D protein models to find the most stable shapes. This matters because a protein's shape determines how it works in the body. Computers often have trouble predicting the best folds, but human creativity and intuition can find new solutions. When players submit their folded proteins, scientists study them to better understand how proteins work and misfold – helping to develop treatments for diseases like cancer, Alzheimer's, and COVID-19.

An interesting fact: In 2011, Foldit players helped solve the structure of an AIDS-related enzyme that scientists had been unable to figure out for over a decade!

[Explore the Foldit project sheet](#) and check out the video below to discover more!

2.7 Citizen Science Project Examples for the Ocean and Waters Mission

Now it's the turn of the Ocean and Waters Mission!

This section highlights five projects that invite students and communities to collect and share valuable data on marine debris, plastic pollution, river dynamics, and water quality.

Remember: You don't need to explore every project or information sheet – just focus on the ones that interest you or fit best with your teaching context!

2.7.1 Marine Debris Tracker

Let's present the first project for the blue mission!

[Marine Debris Tracker](#) is a citizen science initiative that empowers individuals to document and combat plastic pollution and other forms of litter in any environment – from remote coastlines to urban streets and waterways.

[Check out the Marine Debris Tracker project sheet here.](#)

2.7.2 Plastic Pirates

Another project on plastic pollution is Plastic Pirates!

[Plastic Pirates](#) focuses on understanding the extent and composition of plastic litter in freshwater environments. Participants, often school classes and youth groups, actively collect, sort, and document litter samples using scientific methods. By contributing their findings to a central database, they help scientists fill crucial research gaps on plastic pollution, inform policy decisions, and raise broader public awareness about the journey of plastic from land to sea.

[Read through the Marine Debris Tracker project sheet here!](#)

2.7.3 DRYVER

Ever seen a river disappear?

[DRYVER](#) is a citizen science project that invites participants to track how rivers change – sometimes flowing fast, sometimes pooling, and sometimes drying up entirely. Across Europe, many rivers don't run year-round, and as climate change and human activity reshape our environment, these

temporary rivers are more important (and more threatened) than ever. By visiting a local river or stream and reporting its current condition, your students can help scientists understand how these ecosystems work and how we can protect them.

[Open the DRYvER project sheet to explore more!](#)

2.7.4 Eye on Water

Ever wondered what the colour of water can tell us?

With [Eye on Water](#), students become environmental detectives, using a simple app to observe and record the colour and clarity of water in rivers, lakes, oceans – or even local fountains. These simple, everyday observations contribute to a worldwide effort to monitor water quality and understand the impacts of pollution, algae growth, and sediment!

[Start exploring with the Eye on Water project sheet!](#)

2.7.5 CrowdWater

What if your local stream could help predict the next flood – or drought – halfway across the world?

With [CrowdWater](#), students become hydrologists in the field, using an app to monitor rivers, streams, and soil moisture. By placing a virtual ruler on a reference photo, they track changes in water levels over time. These observations contribute to improving flood and drought forecasting, especially in areas with little or no formal monitoring.

[Access the CrowdWater project sheet here!](#)

2.8 Citizen Science Project Examples for the Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission

Imagine a city shaped by the people who live in it – designed for comfort, sustainability, and smarter living. That's the goal of climate-neutral and smart cities. But turning that vision into reality takes more than big ideas; it needs real data, knowledge, and everyday observations from the people who live there.

Citizen science brings those voices to life, helping create cities that work better for everyone.

Let's explore four project examples designed to improve our cities!

2.8.1 Hush City

In the midst of city noise, finding a quiet spot can feel like a rare discovery. **But what if you could help uncover and protect these hidden pockets of calm?**

With the [Hush City](#) project, students use simple tools to measure noise levels and reflect on how different places sound and feel. Their insights contribute to a growing map of quiet urban spaces – helping reimagine how cities support well-being and everyday life.

Join the movement to make our cities more liveable – [start by exploring the Hush City project sheet here!](#)

2.8.2 hackAir

What's really in the air we breathe each day – and how can we find out for ourselves?

[hackAIR](#) combines a wide network of data – from official stations and satellites to low-cost sensors and personal observations – to build a real-time, easy-to-understand picture of the air in your area. Even without a sensor, you can take part by simply noting what you see, smell, or feel in the air around you.

[Learn more through the HackAir project sheet!](#)

2.8.3 Globe at Night

When was the last time you saw a sky truly full of stars?

In today's world, the dazzling beauty of the cosmos is often hidden by something you might not usually think of as pollution: light pollution. But what if you could help bring those stars back?

With the [Globe at Night](#) project, you can join people worldwide in protecting our night skies. During special campaigns, all you have to do is step outside, find a constellation, compare it to some easy star charts, and share what you see!

A simple step that helps scientists track light pollution and bring the stars back for everyone!

[Explore all the details in the Globe at Night project sheet.](#)

2.8.4 BiciZen

Want to help make your city more bike-friendly?

[BiciZen](#) lets cyclists turn their rides into useful data about bike lanes, road quality, and safety. Even if you don't bike, you can still get involved by exploring the data, checking out local routes on foot, and coming up with ideas to improve cycling in your area.

It's a great way to combine tech, health, and urban planning while making a real difference in how your city gets around!

[Read through the BiciZen project sheet here!](#)

Ready to explore the projects for the soil mission? Let's continue!

2.9 Citizen Science Project Examples for the Soil Mission

Let's move on to the final set of projects and mission: soil!

In this section, you'll find three simple projects that let you collect real data – on plastic pollution, soil health, and decomposition – and contribute to global soil research.

Ready to get your hands (gloved!) a little dirty for science? Time to explore the soil projects!

2.9.1 SoilPlastic

Plastic pollution isn't just in oceans and rivers – it's in our soils too. From farms to parks to roadsides, tiny pieces of plastic are working their way into the earth, affecting everything from soil health to food production. But most of this pollution goes unseen... until now.

With the [SoilPlastic](#) app, anyone can become a soil detective! By spotting and documenting plastic waste in outdoor environments, you'll help scientists map where soil plastics are found, what kinds are most common, and how widespread the problem really is.

[Read through the SoilPlastic project sheet here!](#)

2.9.2 TeaComposition Initiative

What can a tea bag tell us about the planet?

Quite a lot!

The [TeaComposition Initiative](#) uses green and rooibos tea bags to explore how organic matter breaks down in soils around the world. By comparing results from different climates and landscapes, participants contribute to a better understanding of soil health, the carbon cycle, and the impacts of climate change!

[More about TeaComposition Initiative in this project sheet!](#)

2.9.3 LandPKS

Is your land good for growing crops, grazing animals, or restoring native plants? How much water can it hold? Is it at risk of erosion?

With the [LandPKS app](#), anyone can answer these questions, using just a few simple tools!

[Check out the LandPKS project sheet here!](#)

And that's the last of our projects – we hope you enjoyed exploring them and came away with plenty of new ideas!

2.10 Citizen Science Project Examples – Wrap-Up

2.10.1 Activity: Vote for your favourite project!

You've just explored a wide range of citizen science projects linked to the five EU Missions – there's a lot to take in!

We hope you had the chance to dive into the ones that caught your interest, check out their information sheets, and explore the project websites and resources.

Now, we'd love to hear from you: **Which project was your favourite, or which one do you think has the most potential to engage your students?**

We know – it's not easy to pick just one! 😊

Results gathered from **286** respondents.

2.10.2 Activity: Explain your vote

Now that you’ve voted for your favourite citizen science project, take a moment to reflect on your choice. **Why did this project stand out to you?**

Consider factors like:

- How well fits your teaching goals
- Your students’ interests and skill levels
- The resources and time you have available

[Share your reasoning in the Padlet](#) under the **Mission your project contributes to**.

Don't forget to **mention the name of the project** in your post!

Please note: Posts that are entirely generated by AI and do not contribute meaningfully to the course discussion or exchange will be removed.

2.11 Final Assignment – The CROPS Learning Scenario Template (Step 2)

2.11.1 Develop further your learning scenario

As we approach the end of Module 2, let's take a moment to recap our final course activity: **developing a learning scenario that integrates a citizen science project of your choice!**

By now, you might already have a project in mind – whether it's one of the examples introduced in this module or a different project that better suits your interests or teaching context.

To support your planning, don't forget to use the [Citizen Science Planning Worksheet](#). It's a helpful tool to ensure your selected project meets your needs and educational goals.

If you've already chosen your project, you should now be able to complete the **“Overview”** section of [your learning scenario](#). That's a great milestone!

But if you're still exploring your options, that's absolutely fine. Take the time you need to choose a project that will truly support your students' learning and work well in your setting 😊.

Next week, we'll move on to designing inquiry-based learning activities around your chosen citizen science project – and we'll look at how to make those activities engaging, meaningful, and impactful for your students!

Subject(s)	<p>List the subject or knowledge area that this Learning Scenario is intended for. For example, Chemistry (subject) / Water quality (knowledge area).</p> <p>If this is an interdisciplinary lesson, list all relevant subjects.</p> <p><i>Note: Citizen Science projects often deal with real-world challenges that don't fit into a single subject. Using more than one subject helps students understand the bigger picture and makes learning more meaningful.</i></p>
Topic(s)	<p>Add a topic that the Learning Scenario addresses.</p> <p>For example, if this Learning Scenario is intended for a Science and Geography lesson, the topic could be "Tracking seasonal changes in local biodiversity".</p>
Age of the learners	<p>Write the age group this Learning Scenario is designed for.</p>
Preparation time	<p>Indicate how many hours per subject are needed to prepare this Learning Scenario.</p>
Total implementation time	<p>Indicate how many hours per subject are needed to carry out all the activities described.</p>
Teaching material	<p><u>Online materials and resources:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to tools and platforms (e.g. Padlet, Kahoot, Genially) • Links to supporting content (e.g. YouTube videos, articles, downloadable PDFs) <p><u>Physical materials:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paper, glue, pens, printed worksheets, or other supplies needed
Responsible Use & Student Privacy	<p>Reflect on how you will ensure students' data and privacy are protected. Consider aspects such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the need for parental or guardian consent, • the use of teacher- or school-managed accounts instead of individual ones, and • avoiding the upload of personal or identifiable information (faces, names, or precise locations).

2.12 Module Round-Up

2.12.1 Want to dive deeper?

If you're eager to keep going and want to learn more about developing effective citizen science projects for your students, these resources are a great next step!

They offer practical strategies, planning tools, and real-world examples to help you design engaging, meaningful learning experiences that work in your specific teaching context.

Toolkits and Guides:

[Citizen Science Toolkit: Teaching Science Through Citizen Science](#): Tips and materials for bringing citizen science into your classroom.

[Guide to Choosing Locally Relevant Citizen Science Projects for the Classroom](#): Helps you find projects that align with your curriculum and local environment.

[Schoolyard SITES Curriculum Workbook](#): A Design Process for Engaging Students in Citizen Science in Their Schoolyard: A step-by-step guide for creating hands-on projects using your own schoolyard.

Publications:

[Turning Students into Citizen Scientists](#): A look at how citizen science can turn your students into real contributors to scientific research.

2.12.2 Apply to be a presenter at the TeachMeet

Before you go, here's a special opportunity!

Our **course TeachMeet** will take place on **Thursday, 6 November, at 17:00 CET**. This live event is your chance to share your ideas, activities, or early Learning Scenario drafts with fellow participants.

If you'd like to be one of our speakers, please [fill in this form](#) by **Tuesday, 28 October**. Spots are limited, so don't miss your chance to inspire others and showcase your work!

2.12.3 Summary

Great work! We have made it through Module 2 😊

- ✓ You analysed the key factors that determine whether a citizen science project is a good fit for your classroom.
- ✓ You evaluated how different projects align with curriculum goals, student skills, and practical classroom constraints.
- ✓ You explored a wide range of citizen science projects connected to the five EU Missions.
- ✓ You took the first steps in developing your learning scenario and identified the project you'll be working with.

Next module starts on Monday. Keep up the good work!

3 Module 3: Planning and Implementing Citizen Science Activities

3.1 Welcome to Module 3!

"Tell me and I forget. Teach me and I remember. Involve me and I learn."

Benjamin Franklin

Last week, in **Module 2**, we discovered citizen science projects linked to the five EU Missions and learned how to choose ones that fit our classroom context.

Now, in **Module 3**, we'll move from choosing a project to involving our students in it. This module is divided into three parts:

- ✓ **First**, you'll explore five citizen science Learning Scenarios (one for each EU Mission) created by CROPS teachers, offering a behind-the-scenes look at how other educators planned, organised, and engaged their students in citizen science projects.
- ✓ **Second**, you'll reflect on the strategies these teachers used to integrate citizen science into their teaching.
- ✓ **Third**, you'll explore how the stages of the scientific inquiry process link to citizen science projects, and learn strategies to design activities where students contribute to real research.

Finally, remember: to receive a certificate of course completion, you'll need to submit a **Learning Scenario** based on an existing citizen science project that is connected to one of the five EU Missions. This module will guide you in drafting the **Activities section** of your scenario.

Important notice:

This module includes interactive activities (Padlets, Tricider, Forums) where you'll share your own ideas and experiences. Please complete these on your own – without AI tools – so the discussions stay authentic and meaningful. And remember, your peers are just a post away if you need support 😊.

3.2 Citizen Science Learning Scenarios Examples

3.2.1 Introduction to the CROPS learning scenarios

Let's get started – and what better way than by exploring other teachers' Learning Scenarios!

Before you dive in, a couple of quick tips:

- Have a pen and paper ready to note down any activities or ideas you like – we'll ask you about them later!
- You don't need to review every scenario. If time is short, focus on those that best match your subject or age group, and don't miss the teacher interviews for quick, practical insights.

Ready to explore your first Learning Scenario!

3.2.2 Learning Scenario 1 (Climate Adaptation) – “Tiger Mosquito Detectives: A Citizen Science Challenge”

Our first Learning Scenario comes from **Quique Vergara** and is linked to the **EU Mission on Climate Adaptation**.

Designed for **students aged 14–17**, it can be integrated across subjects such as **biology, geography, or maths**. In this project, students take on the role of citizen scientists investigating the spread of the Asian tiger mosquito – a species that thrives in warmer conditions and is closely tied to climate change and public health challenges.

Using the [Mosquito Alert app](#), students collect and upload local data on mosquito sightings and breeding sites, analyse patterns with climate data, and propose community-based solutions to reduce risks.

Link to the Learning Scenario on Scientix:

<https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131020>

As you can see, this Learning Scenario makes scientific inquiry **tangible and purposeful**, guiding students through the full process of how science works in real life:

ASKING QUESTIONS

Students brainstorm and generate research questions like “Where are the most common breeding sites in our

	neighbourhood?” or “How does standing water affect mosquito populations?”.
FORMING HYPOTHESES	They create testable predictions, e.g., “We expect to find more tiger mosquitoes near areas with dense vegetation and standing water.”
PLANNING AND INVESTIGATING	Students design observation routes and learn data protocols with the Mosquito Alert app.
COLLECTING DATA	They carry out fieldwork, recording sightings, environmental factors, and uploading geo-referenced data with photos.
ANALYSING AND INTERPRETING	Students organise findings in spreadsheets, clean datasets and compare results with open data from Mosquito Alert. They create graphs, charts, and maps to identify patterns and link them to local climate data.
DRAWING CONCLUSIONS	Students revisit research questions and hypotheses to explain patterns between climate conditions and mosquito presence.
COMMUNICATING RESULTS	They share findings through campaigns: posters, infographics, presentations, or social media.

[Now, let's hear from Quique about his Learning Scenario!](#)

3.2.3 Learning Scenario 2 (Oceans & Waters) – Waters in Our Hands: A Citizen Science Journey with Marine Debris Tracker

Our second Learning Scenario, created by course moderator **Anita Šimac**, is linked to the **EU Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters by 2030**.

It shows that citizen science isn't just for older learners – even **10–12-year-olds** can collect valid data, think critically, and take action on global challenges like marine pollution.

Working across **science, geography, maths, ICT, and civic education**, students use the [Marine Debris Tracker app](#) to map and record litter in their local environment – from schoolyards and parks to riversides and city streets. They document the types and amounts of debris, analyse patterns such as hotspots or common items, and connect their findings to bigger questions like *“How does local litter contribute to ocean pollution?”*

But the work doesn't end with data collection. Students translate evidence into action by drafting **Community Action Plans** – proposing clean-ups, awareness campaigns, or even policy changes.

Just like in Quique’s scenario, students experience the full cycle of inquiry: asking questions, forming hypotheses, collecting and analysing data, and drawing evidence-based conclusions.

Link to the Learning Scenario on Scientix:

<https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131022>

[Now, let’s hear from Anita about her Learning Scenario!](#)

3.2.4 Learning Scenario 3 (Climate-Neutral & Smart Cities) – Assessing Urban Public Spaces: A Citizen Science Approach with Our Outdoors

Our third Learning Scenario, by **Achillefs Kapartzianis**, links to the **EU Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities**.

Aimed at **16–18-year-olds**, it turns students into *urban investigators*. Using tools like thermometers, light meters, and humidity sensors, they measure environmental conditions such as air and surface temperature, lighting, and humidity. At the same time, they use the [Our Outdoors](#) citizen science app

to record their *emotional responses* – for example, how happy, calm, safe, or comfortable they feel in a particular space.

Working across **science**, **geography**, **physics**, **architecture**, and **psychology**, they analyse their findings and propose ideas to make urban areas greener, more inclusive, and climate-resilient.

Link to the Learning Scenario on Scientix:

<https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131021>

What makes this Learning Scenario stand out is how Achillefs adapted the [Our Outdoors](#) project for classroom use. The app is designed mainly to capture people’s emotional responses to public spaces – for example, how safe, calm, or happy they feel. To turn this into a full scientific inquiry, Achillefs asked students to also measure environmental factors such as temperature, light, and humidity.

By combining emotional responses with scientific measurements, students move beyond simply describing their feelings. They investigate deeper questions like “*How do environmental conditions influence people’s comfort and well-being in public spaces?*”

This approach gives students hands-on experience in inquiry-based science: they learn to collect and analyse data, connect evidence to human experience, and propose improvements for more inclusive, climate-resilient cities. At the same time, their findings feed directly into the Our Outdoors project, making a real contribution to urban research.

[Listen to Achillefs explain more about his Learning Scenario in the video!](#)

3.2.5 Learning Scenario 4 (Soil) – Is Our Schoolyard Soil Healthy? Investigating Soil Properties Using the LandPKS App

Time to get our hands dirty!

Our fourth Learning Scenario, designed by **Eleni Papadopoulou**, links to the **EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe**.

In this project, students become *soil detectives*, asking the big question: “*Is our schoolyard soil healthy and sustainable?*”

Using the [LandPKS app](#), they measure soil texture, slope, land cover, and other indicators, while simple hands-on experiments help them explore concepts like water absorption, erosion risk, and organic matter.

Working across **natural sciences, maths, ICT**, and **civic education**, students collect and analyse soil data, then design a School Soil Health Plan with practical actions to protect and improve their local soil.

The scenario is designed for **10–12-year-olds**, but it can easily be adapted for older learners too.

Link to the Learning Scenario on Scientix:

<https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131003>

As you can see, students don't need to leave their schoolyard to contribute to scientific research 😊

[Hear Eleni explain more about her Learning Scenario in the video!](#)

3.2.6 Learning Scenario 5 (Cancer) – Curly or Straight? Learning Protein Structure through Foldit and Citizen Science

Our fifth and final Learning Scenario, designed by **Teresita Gravina**, connects to the **EU Mission on Cancer**.

Here, **15–18-year-old** students dive into molecular biology with [Foldit](#) – a citizen science game where players solve 3D protein-folding puzzles. By experimenting with hydrogen bonds, alpha helices, beta sheets, and side chains, they see how protein structures shape function – and how misfolding can cause diseases like cancer.

What makes this scenario special is its playful, game-based approach. Instead of just reading about proteins, students *learn by doing* – folding, testing, and problem-solving in Foldit. And their solutions don't stay in the classroom: they contribute to scientific research!

Link to the Learning Scenario on Scientix:

<https://www.scientix.eu/resources/knowledge/teaching-materials/teaching-material?id=131002>

[Let's listen to Teresita as she shares more about her Learning Scenario!](#)

3.2.7 Activity: Reflecting on best practices in citizen science learning scenarios

Now it's your turn!

After exploring the five Learning Scenarios (or some of them), [go to the Padlet and share your reflections.](#)

You can focus on one scenario that stood out to you or draw comparisons across several. Don't forget to read what others have posted – and feel free to like or comment on their ideas!

3.3 Fostering Scientific Inquiry in the Classroom

3.3.1 Fostering scientific inquiry in the classroom (Introduction)

Now that you've seen how other teachers involve their students in citizen science projects, it's time to take a closer look at *how* this works in practice.

In this second half of Module 3, we'll focus on the **scientific inquiry process** – a structured yet flexible framework that helps teachers turn citizen science projects into meaningful learning experiences.

Citizen science isn't just about sharing data. It's about guiding students to **think and act like scientists**: asking questions, testing ideas, analysing evidence, and communicating results.

Along the way, they don't just contribute to research – they gain critical skills that will serve them well beyond the classroom.

Ready to begin the inquiry journey!

3.3.2 Before we dive in: A note on inquiry

Before we jump into the first step, there's something important to remember.

When engaging students in scientific activities, it's important to **communicate to them that the scientific method is not a rigid, step-by-step recipe**. Real investigations – including citizen science projects – often loop back and forth between asking questions, testing ideas, and refining approaches as new insights emerge.

Making this clear shows students that unexpected results aren't failures, but opportunities to discover and learn more. It also helps them build adaptability and resilience when things don't go exactly as planned.

Throughout this module, we'll keep coming back to the scientific inquiry framework as we plan how to engage students at each stage of their citizen science experience.

3.4 Observing, Questioning and Hypothesising

3.4.1 Drafting scientifically testable questions

How can we help students turn curiosity into investigation?

A cornerstone of scientific inquiry – and of any citizen science project – is asking **scientifically testable questions**. Students are naturally curious, but not all questions can be explored in class or within a project's scope. Your role is to help them refine broad ideas into questions that are **specific, measurable, and testable**:

CHARACTERISTIC	DESCRIPTION
Specific	Focused on an observable phenomenon, not too broad or abstract.
Measurable	Answered with quantifiable data or clear observations.
Testable	Investigated through an experiment or observation (not opinion-based).

For example, a student might say: *“I notice more birds in the yard when it’s quiet.”* That’s a great start, but not yet testable. Together, you can refine it into: *“Do birds visit the schoolyard more often during quiet times than noisy times?”* Now the question has measurable conditions (noise level/time of day) and an observable outcome (number of birds).

Sorting Questions Tool. Adapted from the [Schoolyard SITES Curriculum Workbook](#).

A simple strategy is [a question sort activity](#). Students brainstorm as many questions as they can about a topic, then sort them into “testable” and “non-testable.” Non-testable ones might include big “Why” questions like *“Why do mosquitoes exist?”* or ones that are too broad like *“How can we stop climate change?”* These are valid wonders, but they’re not questions we can test directly.

Testable questions usually explore **relationships between variables** and follow the format: “*What is the relationship between X and Y?*” or “*How does X affect Y?*”. For example:

- “*What is the relationship between tree canopy cover and temperature underneath?*”
- “*Does the amount of fertilizer affect plant height?*”

To practice, you might give students a scenario and some example questions, and have them critique which are testable. For instance, if the topic is soil moisture:

- “*Will it rain more this year?*” → Too broad.
- “*Does adding compost help soil hold more water?*” → Testable.
- “*Why is soil important?*” → Too general.
- “*Which soil type dries out fastest: sand, clay, or loam?*” → Testable.

The key is to remind students that **drafting good questions takes practice**. They may begin vague, but with your guidance, they can refine their ideas into focused, testable questions that drive real investigations.

3.4.2 When contributing to citizen science projects

Unlike a typical classroom experiment, where students design many of the steps themselves, most citizen science projects come with **research questions and data collection methods defined by scientists**.

This doesn't limit students – it actually positions them as **co-investigators** in a much larger effort. By contributing observations and analyses, they help answer real scientific questions at scale. That sense of authenticity is often what motivates them most!

Even within this framework, there's plenty of room for curiosity and critical thinking. Students can:

- **Connect** their own questions and wonderings to the project's focus.
- **Refine** sub-questions that fit within the project's methods (for example, a class might come up with a local question like “*Which tree in our schoolyard has the most bird sightings?*” within a bigger bird migration project).

- **Reflect** on design choices, considering why scientists structured the questions and protocols the way they did. (*Why do we need to take water temperature and pH? Why photograph the mosquito breeding site instead of just describing it?*)

Through this, students learn not only to contribute to real science, but also to understand how strong questions drive reliable data and meaningful discoveries.

3.4.3 Formulating hypotheses based on observations

Once students understand the project's main question, they can still **practise formulating hypotheses** – even if the project already defines one.

A good hypothesis clarifies what students expect to happen and why.

✓ Hypothesis Checklist

When evaluating their hypotheses, students can ask themselves:

1. Have I identified the independent variable (what I change) and the dependent variable (what I measure)?
2. Is my hypothesis specific and testable, rather than vague or based on opinion?
3. Did I include a reason or explanation for why I expect this outcome?

Here are some strategies to guide students:

1. **Build on observations and science concepts:** A hypothesis isn't a random guess – it's an informed prediction. For example, noticing that plants near a window grow taller could lead to: *"If a plant gets more sunlight, then it will grow taller because sunlight provides energy for photosynthesis."* Or, applying science knowledge: *"If the ground is darker, then it will heat up faster in sunlight because darker surfaces absorb more heat."*
2. **Use a simple structure:** The frame *"If ___ (I change this), then ___ (this will happen), because ___ (reason)"* helps students include all the key parts: condition, result, and rationale. For example: *"If we collect litter near bus stops, then we will find more plastic bottles, because people often drink while waiting and discard containers there."*

- 3. Keep it measurable:** A hypothesis should connect to something students can observe or quantify. For instance, if the question is *“Does music affect how fast people type?”* the hypothesis could be: *“People will type faster when listening to upbeat music because the rhythm increases alertness and speed.”* This works because the outcome (typing speed in words per minute) is measurable.
- 4. Stay aligned with the project:** Hypotheses should connect to the project’s focus and be testable using its data collection steps. Reviewing these steps with students before they draft hypotheses makes the process smoother.

Finally, remind students that **a hypothesis doesn’t need to be “right.”** It’s a starting point for investigation. If the data doesn’t support it, that’s not failure – it’s an important finding. In science, disproving a hypothesis can be just as valuable as confirming one 😊.

Emphasise that *“What does the data show?”* is more important than *“Were we correct?”*.

3.4.4 Activity: Unlocking inquiry

Now it’s your turn to try out the first steps of scientific investigation!

[In the Padlet below](#), you’ll find five columns – one for each EU Mission. Under the column that matches the mission of the citizen science project you’ve chosen for your Learning Scenario (Module 2), create a post that includes:

- 1. Project name.**
- 2. Observation** – Something students could realistically notice or record in this project.
- 3. Testable question** – A specific, measurable question derived from that observation. This can be the project’s main question or a related sub-question.
- 4. Hypothesis** – A prediction that students could investigate using the project’s data collection methods.

👏 **Peer feedback:** After posting, read at least one peer’s entry and leave a short comment. Focus on whether their question and hypothesis is **specific**, **measurable**, and **testable** – and suggest how they could refine it if needed.

3.5 Developing a Plan (Introduction)

With a solid question and hypothesis, the next step is figuring out how to test them. In citizen science projects, the research design is usually already set by scientists – your role is to **adapt it for your classroom**.

Think of it as creating a bridge between the scientists' plan and your lesson plan. You'll be deciding things like: Who will do what? What preparations or materials are needed? How will we ensure the data we collect is valid?

Essentially, **how can we set up our students for success as contributors to this project?**

3.5.1 Let's explore further! Designing an investigation

Designing an investigation doesn't mean starting from scratch. It means working within the project's framework while planning the practical details that make it run smoothly in school: methods, timing, roles, sampling strategy, and preparation.

By taking the time to map this out, you'll make sure students can focus on inquiry and discovery, rather than confusion or logistics.

 Try to bring students into the planning stage where you can. Let them have a say in things like where to do the fieldwork, what extra observations might be worth noting, or how to split into groups. When students feel the plan is partly theirs, they're usually more motivated and also get some real practice in planning and decision-making.

[In this Genially, we present seven key areas to consider:](#)

DESIGNING AN INVESTIGATION

CLICK + TO LEARN MORE ABOUT EACH ELEMENT!

METHODS AND TOOLS

TIMELINE

STUDENT ROLES

SAMPLING STRATEGY

CONTROLS AND FAIR TESTS

INTEGRATION WITH CITIZEN SCIENCE PLATFORM

MATERIALS PREPARATION

Funded by the European Union

Project funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This MOOC is also supported by Scientix®, an initiative of European Schoolnet.

3.5.2 Training students in data collection protocols

In citizen science projects, data quality is crucial – after all, the data might be used by researchers, and even if not, we want students to base conclusions on accurate information. That’s why most projects come with carefully designed **protocols** – and why students need support to follow them correctly.

 Why is this important? If everyone collects data differently, the results quickly become messy or invalid. And if students aren’t confident with the protocol, they may make mistakes or feel frustrated. A bit of training upfront prevents these issues and sets students up for success!

Here are some strategies to prepare students for accurate and confident data collection:

- 1. Explain the “why” behind each step:** Students are more motivated to follow instructions when they know why they matter. For instance, if the protocol requires a photo of the *whole* plant, explain that scientists need to see the context to verify the species.
- 2. Demonstrate it live:** Whenever possible, model the process yourself or show a video of someone doing it.
- 3. Do a practice run:** Before heading into the “real” fieldwork, let students rehearse in a low-stakes setting. For example, before a water quality project at a stream, practice by testing water from a bucket in class. If using an app like eBird for bird counting, do a 5-minute mock birdwatch in the schoolyard to practice identifying and logging. This way, students get to ask questions and you can correct technique on the spot.
- 4. Simplify instructions:** Official protocols might be lengthy or written for adults. Consider creating a one-page checklist or visual guide in student-friendly language. Something they can carry with them in the field will keep everyone on track.
- 5. Talk through pitfalls and “what ifs”:** Anticipate tricky situations together. What if students can’t identify a bird? (Mark it “unknown” or take a photo.) What if a flock flies by too fast to count? (Note it in the comments.) Show how to correct errors in the app or data sheet, so they know mistakes can be fixed properly.

- 6. Highlight responsibility:** Remind students that they're not just doing a class activity – their contributions may be part of real science. Accuracy and honesty matter more than “perfect” results. Encourage them to think of themselves as collaborators whose data others will rely on.

3.5.3 Activity: From question to protocol

In the last activity, you drafted a question and hypothesis for the citizen science project you want your students to contribute to. Now it's time to explore *how* they will test it – by looking closely at the project's **protocol**.

👉 Go to your project's website and review the resources provided (e.g., instructions, videos, checklists, teacher guides). [Then, in the Padlet, answer this question:](#)

Describe the protocol in simple words and explain how you would support your students in following it successfully.

💡 Don't forget to include the name of your project, so you can connect with other teachers who may be working on the same one for their Learning Scenarios!

Add your post under the column for the EU Mission your project addresses.

3.6 Investigating and Gathering Data

3.6.1 Conducting data collection with students

Now comes one of the most exciting stages – collecting data! 🎉

This is where your students step into the role of real citizen scientists: observing, measuring, recording, and contributing to research. Whether it's outside in the field, inside a lab, or even online, this is the point where all the planning becomes action.

As a teacher, your role shifts from **planner** to **facilitator** – guiding, supporting, and solving problems on the spot.

It can get a little noisy and messy, but that's part of authentic science. This is where learning feels most alive! 😊

3.6.2 Quiz: Data collection best practices

To help you prepare for the unpredictable moments of fieldwork, let's test your readiness with a quick 5-question quiz on best practices.

Q1. Two groups are measuring soil temperature in the schoolyard as part of a climate project. One group records 18°C, the other 23°C in the same spot at the same time. What should they do?

- a) Average the two results and submit them
- b) Repeat the measurement together, checking that they use the same method
- c) Keep the higher value, since it shows more warming
- d) Report both values without comment

👉 *Explanation:* Inconsistent results often come from different techniques (e.g., one group placed the thermometer deeper). Repeating together ensures consistent methods and reliable data.

Q2. A mosquito-mapping project asks students to photograph each sighting. Some students say they forgot but wrote notes instead. What's the best response?

- a) Accept the notes – more data is always good
- b) Ask them to draw the mosquito from memory
- c) Remind them photos are required for species verification and repeat the activity with photos
- d) Submit the notes and add a disclaimer

👉 *Explanation:* Protocol steps exist for a reason. Here, the photo allows scientists to confirm the species. Better to repeat correctly than risk submitting unusable data.

Q3. During a bird survey, the app crashes, and students lose their entries. What's best?

- a) Stop collecting data for the day
- b) Record on paper and upload later
- c) Try to re-enter from memory at home
- d) Skip that round of data

👉 *Explanation:* Always have a low-tech backup. Paper sheets ensure observations aren't lost and can be uploaded later.

Q4. During soil sampling, a group forgets to record moisture levels for one site. What should they do?

- a) Leave it blank and mark "missing data"
- b) Make up a value based on nearby sites

- c) Delete the entire sample
- d) Replace it with a guess from the teacher

👉 *Explanation:* Guessing undermines data quality. Marking “missing” keeps the dataset honest and still useful.

Q5. In a litter survey, students get bored after counting their 30th candy wrapper. What’s one good practice to keep motivation up while ensuring accuracy?

- a) Allow students to stop early
- b) Skip repeating categories
- c) Let them record estimates instead of counts
- d) Turn it into a team challenge with goals

👉 *Explanation:* Repetition can reduce motivation. Framing the task as a challenge or setting collective goals keeps energy high while ensuring every item is counted accurately.

3.6.3 Did you know?

You’ve just explored how to prepare students for quality data collection – but what happens after they submit their observations through a citizen science app or website?

In many cases, their data doesn’t stop there. Instead, it is forwarded to **open data repositories**. These platforms make the data **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)**, so it can be used by researchers, policymakers, and communities across Europe.

The [CROPS Deliverable D4.1 – Review of Open Data Repositories](#) analysed how different EU Mission-related projects connect to Europe’s open data infrastructure.

A few key examples include:

- [Copernicus Climate Data Store \(CDS\)](#): Free, open access to climate datasets, widely used for adaptation and monitoring.
- [EMODnet \(European Marine Observation and Data Network\)](#): A hub for marine and coastal biodiversity, habitats, and human activities.
- [GBIF \(Global Biodiversity Information Facility\)](#): An international network sharing biodiversity records from projects such as iNaturalist.

- [ESDAC \(European Soil Data Centre\)](#): Centralised EU hub for soil-related data, maps, and assessments.
- [OpenStreetMap \(OSM\)](#): A global, open-source mapping platform enriched by citizen contributions, often used in urban planning.
- [Protein Data Bank in Europe \(PDBe\)](#): Repository for protein structures, relevant to biomedical research and projects like Foldit.

That means that by contributing through citizen science projects connected to these repositories, students' observations can feed directly into European and even global knowledge systems. Their work might one day inform climate reports, marine protection, soil policies, or urban planning decisions!

3.7 Analysing, Interpreting and Thinking Critically

3.7.1 Making sense of data

After a successful data collection phase, students will likely have a lot of raw data: numbers, observations, photographs, or maps.

Now it's time to make sense of this material, turning it into evidence that can be analysed, visualised, and interpreted to answer the questions they posed.

So, how can we support our students in working with their data? **Next, you'll explore some strategies!**

3.7.2 Choosing the right tool

The tool you choose depends on your students' age, prior knowledge, and the kind of data collected. Here are some options:

- **Spreadsheet software.** Programs like [Microsoft Excel](#), [Google Sheets](#), or [LibreOffice Calc](#) allow students to enter data into tables, perform basic calculations (sum, average, etc.), and create charts (pie charts, bar graphs, line graphs) with a few clicks. For younger students, you might prepare a template with pre-labelled columns and embedded charts. Then, they only need to enter numbers and immediately see visual changes.
- **Student-friendly analysis tools:** Platforms like [CODAP](#) (Common Online Data Analysis Platform) or [Tuva](#) were designed for classrooms.

They allow drag-and-drop analysis, have built-in datasets, and often feature citizen science examples.

- **Mapping tools:** If your data has a location component (e.g., mosquito sightings, litter hotspots), you can use [Google MyMaps](#) or a simple GIS tool provided by the project (e.g., [Marine Debris Tracker interactive map](#)).
- **Advanced tools:** For older students, there are more sophisticated options such as data visualisation software like [Tableau](#) or programming languages like [Python](#) and [R](#).

It's important to remember that you don't need complex or expensive software – just a tool that matches your students' abilities and helps them **identify patterns** in the data they've collected.

Once you've chosen a tool, move on to the next steps!

3.7.3 Step 1: Data cleaning

Before jumping into analysis, students may need to do a bit of “data cleaning.” This involves reviewing their dataset for mistakes, inconsistencies, or unusual values that could affect results.

Common issues might include:

- Duplicate entries (e.g., two groups recording the same tree or litter pile).
- Impossible values (e.g., soil temperature recorded as 500°C instead of 5°C).
- Inconsistent units (one group wrote cm, another m).

It's valuable for students to understand that scientists regularly spend time checking and cleaning data before moving on to analysis.

3.7.4 Step 2: Calculations

Once data has been cleaned and checked for errors, students can begin working with it. Calculations are an essential step in moving from raw observations to evidence-based conclusions.

 Tips for teachers:

Keep it age-appropriate: Younger students might just count and compare totals (“we found more plastic than paper”), while older ones can calculate averages, ratios, or even correlations.

Use technology to help: Spreadsheets (Google Sheets, Excel, LibreOffice) can do much of this automatically once data is entered. Teaching students simple formulas like =SUM(), =AVERAGE(), or how to create a frequency table is a practical skill they’ll use beyond this project.

Emphasise meaning over math: The goal isn’t complex statistics, but helping students see patterns. Always tie the calculation back to the question or hypothesis: *What does this number tell us? How does it connect to what we were testing?*

3.7.5 Step 3: Choosing and creating the right visualisations

Different questions call for different graphs. Help students think: What do I want to show?

Some examples:

- If they want to compare categories (e.g., types of litter found: plastic vs paper vs metal), a bar chart might be best.
- If they tracked something over time (e.g., temperature each day at noon for two weeks), a line graph shows trends.
- If looking at the composition of something (e.g., percentages of land cover types in different spots), a pie chart or stacked bar could work.
- If dealing with locations, a map with markers can show spatial patterns (like all the mosquito sightings clustering near water).

 Resource: [The Data Visualisation Catalogue](#) is a great tool for deciding which chart fits which question.

Ensure every graph has a title, labelled axes (if relevant, with units!), and maybe a brief caption.

This step is often motivating – it’s where raw numbers become something students can see and explain!

3.7.6 Step 4: Reading and interpreting graphs

A graph is not the end of analysis – it’s the beginning of interpretation. This is where critical thinking comes in.

We need to help students *learn to think like scientists*: examining the evidence and figuring out what it means, what might have influenced it, and whether it supports their initial ideas.

Tips for guiding students:

- 1. Approach data with curiosity and scepticism:** Teach students not to take results at face value. Ask, “Does this make sense? Why or why not?” If something looks odd, explore possible reasons: *“We expected more bees in the garden, but our data shows more in the parking lot – could something be off, or is there an explanation?”* Maybe the garden had pesticides sprayed – an external factor – or maybe students misidentified flies as bees in the parking lot.
- 2. Evaluate data quality:** Discuss things like sample size (*“We only observed for one day – is that enough to draw a conclusion, or could it be a fluke?”*) and consistency (*“Two groups got very different results – what might that tell us?”*). If there were known issues during collection, bring them up: *“Remember our thermometer issue? Perhaps our temperature data for Site 2 might be a bit off. How could that affect our conclusions?”*
- 3. Revisit hypotheses:** Have students go back to the hypotheses they made. Do the data support or refute them? It’s important to stress that not supporting a hypothesis is okay. In fact, it’s often how science progresses. For each hypothesis, they should cite what evidence they have. For example, *“Hypothesis: more birds in quiet times. Our data showed on average 5 birds during class break (noisy) and 6 birds after school (quiet) – not a big difference, so our hypothesis wasn’t strongly supported.”* Encourage language like “supported” or “not supported” rather than “right” or “wrong.”
- 4. Draw evidence-based conclusions:** Guide students to summarise what they found, but always tying it to data. Instead of *“Site A is polluted,”* they should conclude *“Site A had 45 pieces of litter, which was three times more than Site B, indicating it’s more polluted.”* Essentially, the conclusion should be a claim backed by data.

- 5. Consider next questions:** Critical thinking also means thinking ahead. “What new questions do our results raise?” Maybe: *“We found more mosquitoes in the shady area – we wonder if that’s due to humidity. We could measure that next time.”* This shows that science is an ongoing process.
- 6. Recognise limitations:** Help them list what they would do differently or what limits their confidence. *“We only surveyed in fall; perhaps results differ in summer.” “Our sample size of 2 ponds is small; more ponds would give a clearer picture.”* This doesn’t negate their work; it simply frames the scope.
- 7. Comparing to other data or expected results:** Whenever possible, have students compare their findings to existing data or reports from the citizen science project. Do their results align, or are there differences? If there’s a mismatch, discuss possible reasons – maybe they studied a different region, collected data in another season, or ran into data quality issues. If the results do align, celebrate it as validation: *“You found almost the same pattern that scientists reported last year – that shows you followed the method carefully!”* Either way, the comparison helps students think critically about how their work fits into the bigger scientific picture.
- 8. Promote constructive critique:** Encourage an environment where students feel comfortable pointing out flaws or unexpected outcomes. You can even celebrate a thoughtful critique: *“Excellent point, that we observed at different times of day, which might affect results. That’s exactly what scientists do – identify what might have influenced their experiment.”*

 By building this habit of critical reflection, students not only deepen their understanding of the project but also learn how to approach any information or claim in life with a thoughtful, analytical mindset – one that asks, “What’s the evidence?” and “What else could be going on?”

3.7.7 Activity: Working with a dataset

In this activity, you’ll practice guiding students through data analysis using a simple dataset on tree canopy cover and temperature in urban areas.

You’ll answer **six guiding questions**.

Suggested answers are provided for support, but remember – there’s often more than one valid interpretation!

Location	Canopy Cover (%)	Surface Temperature (°C)	Air Temperature (°C)	Notes
City Park	70	28	25	Large shaded areas
Riverside Trail	65	29	26	Near water, shaded path
Residential Street	30	33	30	Trees lining one side
Playground	15	35	32	Open, plastic equipment
Schoolyard	10	36	33	Asphalt, minimal shade
Parking Lot	5	39	35	Asphalt, no trees

If you’d like to practice with the dataset, you can download it as a [CSV file here](#).

Let’s get started!

Exploring the Dataset (Data Familiarisation)

Q1. What patterns or trends do you notice in the data?

Example Answers:

- *Higher canopy cover generally corresponds to lower surface and air temperatures.*
- *Locations with <20% canopy are consistently hotter, especially in surface temperatures.*
- *The surface–air difference is largest in paved areas (e.g., Parking Lot: +4 °C).*

- *Riverside Trail vs City Park shows how water and landscape context can slightly modify temperatures even at similar canopy levels.*

Teacher Tips:

- *Encourage quantitative citations: “The Parking Lot with 5% canopy reached 39 °C surface temp, while the Park with 70% canopy was only 28 °C.”*
- *Prompt critical thinking: “Why might two shaded areas differ? Could water or surface type play a role?”*

Hypothesis Formulation**Q2. Based on the data, what initial hypothesis would you propose?****Example Answers:**

- *“If canopy cover increases, then both surface and air temperatures will decrease because trees provide shade and cooling through evapotranspiration.”*
- *“If canopy cover is below 20%, surface temperature will be at least 7–10 °C higher than in areas with >60% canopy, because shade reduces solar absorption.”*
- *“If the ground is asphalt with little canopy, then its surface temperature will be higher than grassy or shaded surfaces, because asphalt absorbs and stores more heat.”*

Teacher Tips:

- *Encourage use of the If...then...because frame.*
- *Emphasise linking to mechanisms (shade reduces solar heating, evapotranspiration cools air).*
- *Challenge older students to make the hypothesis quantitative (predict a specific difference).*

Identifying Assumptions and Potential Biases**Q3. What biases could affect this data, and how can students spot them?****Example Answers:**

- *Single-day measurement – doesn't show seasonal or diurnal variation.*
- *Air temperature differences are often smaller and harder to detect than surface temperatures; precision matters.*
- *Small sample size (6 sites) may not represent the full city.*
- *Surface materials differ (grass, asphalt, water) – not controlled across sites.*

Teacher Tips:

- *Ask: "How many samples would make this more reliable?" (multiple days/times, seasons, sites).*
- *Show that spotting bias is a strength, not a weakness – professional scientists constantly check for sources of error.*

Visualising the Data

Q4. Which visualisation would help students understand this data best?

Example Answers:

- *Scatter plot of Canopy Cover (%) vs Temperature – shows negative correlation clearly.*

- *Bar chart comparing surface temperatures across locations – simple for younger students.*

- Side-by-side bar chart showing canopy vs surface temperature per site.

Teacher Tips:

- With younger students, keep it simple (bar charts).
- With older students, introduce correlation (scatter plots with trend lines).

Hypothesis Refinement and Interpretation

Q5. How would you adjust the hypothesis based on the data?

Example Answers:

- *“If canopy cover increases, then surface temperatures will decrease by around 10°C, while air temperatures will decrease by around 3°C, because trees provide shade and cooling through evapotranspiration.”*
- *“If an area has less than 20% canopy cover, then its surface temperature will be at least 10°C higher, but its air temperature only about 3°C higher, compared to areas with over 60% canopy, because canopy has a stronger effect on ground heating than on air temperature.”*
- *“If a surface is asphalt with less than 10% canopy cover, then its temperature will be 39°C or higher, while grassy or shaded surfaces will remain closer to 28–30°C, because asphalt absorbs more solar radiation and retains heat longer.”*

Teacher Tips:

- *Guide students to be more precise: from general “trees cool” → to “by how much” and “which temperature measure.”*
- *Encourage considering different variables – e.g., surface vs air, not treating them as the same.*

Drawing Evidence-Based Conclusions

Q6. What conclusions can you draw from the data? What new questions arise?

Example Answers:

Potential Conclusions:

- *Increased canopy cover reduces urban heat, especially surface temperatures.*
- *Air temperatures show smaller but consistent reductions with more canopy.*
- *Surfaces like asphalt intensify heat, especially when unshaded.*

New Questions:

- *How do these patterns change across different times of day (morning vs afternoon)?*

- *Does the effect vary by season (summer vs spring)?*
- *How do surface materials interact with canopy cover in controlling temperature?*
- *What role does proximity to water play (e.g., Riverside Trail)?*

Teacher Tips:

- *Emphasise evidence-based phrasing: “Our data shows...” instead of “I think...”*
- *Remind students that new questions = success: that’s how science moves forward.*

3.7.8 Activity debrief

Great work completing this activity! 🎉

We hope it helped you refresh key tips and skills for guiding students through data analysis and interpretation.

The next step is equally exciting – learning how to communicate scientific results effectively. This means moving from “*what we found*” to “*how we share it*” through clear explanations, visuals, and evidence-based arguments.

But you’ve already covered a lot this week – enough for now!

Next week, we’ll take on this final step of the scientific method together 😊.

3.8 Join our TeachMeet!

Before we wrap up Module 3, here’s a quick reminder: next week in Module 4, we’ll be hosting a **TeachMeet!**

This is a fantastic opportunity to meet other course participants, exchange ideas, and inspire one another with experiences from citizen science in education.

You might, for example:

- Share your **Learning Scenario idea** and get immediate peer feedback.
- Present an **activity that worked well** with your students.

- Tell us about **your experience involving your students** in a citizen science project.

If you'd like to be one of our speakers, don't forget **to fill in this form** before **Tuesday, 28 October, at 23:59 CEST**.

3.9 Final Assignment – The CROPS Learning Scenario Template (Step 3)

3.9.1 Continue working on your Learning Scenario – Plan your activities!

Now, speaking of sharing activities – how is your Learning Scenario coming along?

By now, you've:

- Selected an existing citizen science project contributing to an EU Mission (Module 2).
- Learned strategies for organising and structuring learning activities connected to citizen science projects (Module 3).

That means you're ready to start **planning your activities** and filling in the "Activities" section of [your Learning Scenario template](#). You're doing amazing work – keep it up! 🙌

And don't worry if you're a little behind – the submission deadline is **19 November 2025, 23:59 CET**, so there's still plenty of time.

Step by step, you're moving closer to being accredited as a **citizen science expert teacher**.

3.9.2 Forum: Find your citizen science project and collaborate with others

And remember, you don't have to do this alone!

You're part of a supportive community of teachers in this MOOC. Why not connect in the [Discussion Forum](#) or the [Facebook group](#)?

👉 In the Forum, you can:

- Start a thread with the name of your chosen project (perhaps you find other teachers working on the same project!)
- Exchange ideas on how your Learning Scenario is progressing.

- Ask for advice if you're stuck in the development of your Learning Scenario.

Collaboration is at the heart of citizen science – let's keep building this learning journey together!

3.10 Supporting Resources and Literature

The following resources have been consulted to draft this module, providing research-based foundations and practical guidance on inquiry learning and citizen science in education.

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Shah, H. R., & Martinez, L. R. (2016). Current approaches in implementing citizen science in the classroom. *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education*, 17(1), 17–22.

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<https://theoryandpractice.citizenscienceassociation.org/articles/10.5334/cstp.755>

Tarjan, L. M., de Nesnera, K., & Hoffman, R. (2015). Authentic science investigation in the classroom: Tools for creating original, testable questions and graphical hypotheses. *Science Scope*, 39(4), 42–48.

https://sefhouston.org/wp-content/uploads/AUTHENTIC-SCIENCE-INVESTIGATION-IN-THE-CLASSROOM-SS-_-December-2015.pdf

3.11 Module Round-Up

3.11.1 Summary

Great work! We have made it through Module 3 😊

In this module, you have:

- ✓ Explored five Learning Scenarios (one per EU Mission) to see how other teachers bring citizen science projects into the classroom.
- ✓ Connected each stage of the scientific inquiry process to citizen science projects.
- ✓ Practised drafting testable questions and hypotheses your students can investigate.
- ✓ Planned how to adapt project protocols for your classroom and prepare students for quality data collection.
- ✓ Guided students from raw data → analysis → interpretation, turning observations into evidence and conclusions.

Next module starts on Monday. Keep up the good work!

4 Module 4: Assessing Students' Learning and Impact of Citizen Science Projects

4.1 Welcome to Module 4!

“Citizen science can augment our sense of agency, our sense that we can make a difference in the world.”

Alan Irwin ([in an interview on mit:forschen!](#))

Welcome to Module 4 – the final step of our citizen science journey! 🎉

Over the past weeks, you've explored how to choose, plan, and implement citizen science projects with your students. Now, we'll focus on wrapping everything together: ensuring that your students' learning is visible and impactful.

Therefore, during this module you will:

- ✓ Develop strategies that enable students to effectively communicate scientific findings from citizen science projects.
- ✓ Examine and compare assessment approaches used in citizen science activities, and analyse their role in evaluating student learning.
- ✓ Submit your Learning Scenario.
- ✓ Engage in peer assessment by reviewing peers' work, offering constructive feedback.

Let's get started!

Important notice:

This module includes interactive activities (Padlets, Tricider, Forums) where you'll share your own ideas and experiences. Please complete these on your own – without AI tools – so the discussions stay authentic and meaningful. And remember, your peers are just a post away if you need support 😊.

Ready to start?

4.2 Communicating Scientific Findings

4.2.1 The importance of sharing results

Last week, we ended with interpreting results from citizen science projects. But science doesn't stop there – findings need to be **communicated!**

So, how can we help students share their results with others? After all their effort in planning, collecting, and analysing data, this is the moment for their work to **gain recognition and make an impact.**

Communicating scientific findings is a fundamental stage of any investigation. When students know their work will reach an audience beyond the classroom, they understand that their efforts matter. They see that they can apply what they've learnt to create something real.

Finally, sharing results **amplifies impact.** Whether through presentations, posters, videos, or digital platforms, student findings can inspire peers, inform communities, and contribute knowledge back to the wider citizen science network.

In short, communication turns classroom projects into meaningful contributions!

4.2.2 Choosing the audience and format

An important first step is deciding **who** students will share their findings with and **how** they will do it.

The audience might be their peers and school community through class presentations, assemblies, or [science fairs](#); parents and families during open days; the broader community via local events, social media, or by reaching out to local authorities or scientists; and online platforms where students can post reports, blogs, or digital posters. Each choice helps students see that their work matters and connects classroom learning to the wider world.

The format should always match the audience and the message. Communication needs to be age-appropriate and accessible: younger learners might use simple visuals and keywords, while older students can take on more formal presentations or reports. By aligning medium with message, students gain a key skill in science communication: tailoring information to their audience.

4.2.3 Crafting clear and evidence-based messages

Once the format is set, it's time to help students **shape the content** of their message. This is where they sharpen their science communication skills.

The following tips can guide them:

- 1. Start with the big idea:** Students should identify the one or two main conclusions from their project. *What do they most want their audience to remember?* For example: *“Our schoolyard has low soil nutrients, so we propose starting a compost program,”* or *“We found 200 pieces of litter in our park – plastic was the most common, indicating a need for recycling bins.”* Keeping focus on a clear take-home message prevents the audience from getting lost in details.
- 2. Use the Claim–Evidence–Reasoning structure:** Encourage students to present a **claim** (their conclusion or answer to the research question), back it up with **evidence** (key data points they collected), and provide **reasoning** (an explanation of why the data supports the claim). For example, a student might say: *“We conclude that tree shade cools our playground (claim). The surface temperature under the big oak was 10°C cooler than in the open yard at the same time (evidence). Shade prevents sunlight from heating the ground, so shaded areas stay cooler (reasoning).”*
- 3. Keep it clear and avoid jargon:** If the audience is not made up of experts, students should explain any scientific terms they use. If they mention *“soil nutrients”* they might add *“(the minerals in the soil that plants need to grow).”*
- 4. Make it visual:** A picture is worth a thousand words! Graphs, charts, or maps from their analysis can be powerful in a presentation or poster. Students should label visuals clearly and perhaps add a one-sentence caption to highlight what the audience should notice (*“Map: Mosquito sightings around our town – clusters appear near standing water.”*). If doing a live presentation, students can hold up props or samples (e.g. a jar of local soil they tested, or a printout of a mosquito photo they took) to make it tangible.
- 5. Tell the story of their project:** Encourage a narrative flow: *What question did we start with? How did we investigate it? What did we find? What does it mean?* This storytelling approach keeps the audience interested. For example: *“We noticed something unusual in our school garden... we wondered why some plants were wilting. We*

measured soil moisture in different spots... here's what we found... so we think the problem is poor drainage, and we suggest..."

- 6. Practice and feedback:** Have students rehearse their talks. Peers can give feedback: *Was anything confusing? Did I hear the main point?* If time allows, consider a brief in-class practice session. This will boost their confidence and help polish their explanations before the real presentation.

You can learn more and explore additional resources on this [page!](#)

4.2.4 Activity: Share your communication plan

Now it's your turn to design the grand finale of your students' citizen science project! 🇬🇧

[On the Padlet](#), under the column for the EU Mission of your chosen project, create a post outlining how your students will share their findings. Be sure to include:

- **Audience** – Who will they share with?
- **Means** – Through what channel or setting?
- **Format** – In what form will the results be presented?

When the time comes, students should also help decide *how* and *to whom* they want to present. This will also boost their motivation and make them more invested in the task!

4.3 Assessing Students' Learning in Citizen Science Activities

4.3.1 Types of assessment

How do you know if your students are learning, and how well?

In this unit, we'll explore how to **assess student learning** during citizen science projects.

Let's continue!

4.3.2 Formative, summative and metacognitive assessment

Broadly, assessment is often divided into two main categories: formative and summative. In addition, reflective or metacognitive assessment can be used to help students become more aware of their learning processes.

Formative assessment is often described as assessment for learning. It's the kind of on-the-fly checking for understanding that helps you and your students gauge progress and identify where to adjust. In a citizen science project, formative assessment might include things like observing students as they practice using the data collection protocol, asking quick questions during a field activity ("Why is it important we take the water temperature the same way each time?"), or having students do a brief exit ticket after a lesson (e.g., "Name one pattern you observed in the data today."). The key is that formative assessments are low-stakes and frequent. They're not about giving a grade, but about giving feedback. For example, if you notice many students are confused about how to classify a certain type of litter during the Marine Debris Tracker app, that's a sign to revisit that protocol or provide a clarification. Or if a quick quiz reveals misunderstandings about the difference between hypothesis and prediction, you can address it right away. Formative assessment in citizen science keeps the learning on track while the project is ongoing.

Summative assessment is *assessment of learning*. It takes place at the end of a unit or project and evaluates what students have achieved. In citizen science, the summative element might be a final presentation, poster, or written report communicating findings, or it could be more traditional tools such as a test on concepts covered. A summative assessment should align with your learning objectives. If one objective is for students to understand the steps of scientific inquiry, you might have them write a self-reflection or an essay describing how they went through those steps in their project. If another objective is to learn specific content (say, the life cycle of mosquitoes or the concept of pH in water), you might include targeted questions or ask them to create an annotated diagram demonstrating that knowledge. Summative assessments in citizen science can be very rich because they often encompass skills (like collaboration, data analysis, communication) and content.

Metacognitive (reflective) assessment involves students assessing their own learning – thinking about their thinking. This is especially powerful in inquiry learning. This might involve a journal, a self-assessment checklist, or short prompts such as, "What was the hardest part of this project for me, and how did I handle it?" or "What would I do differently next time?" These reflections make students more aware of their learning strategies and help them develop strategies that help them learn.

Finally, citizen science also lends itself to **peer assessment**, since students often work in teams. Inviting them to comment on each other's

collaboration or contributions teaches accountability and the art of constructive feedback – skills that mirror the collaborative nature of real scientific research.

Taken together, these approaches ensure you're not only measuring what students learnt, but also supporting them in the learning while it's happening.

4.3.3 Assessing the process instead of (or in addition to) the product

In citizen science projects, *how* students learn can be just as important as *what* they produce.

Traditional assessments often emphasise the final outcome – a report, test, or presentation – but citizen science invites us to also value the process: the curiosity, persistence, and skills students develop along the way.

A student's final report might be imperfect, yet the process could reveal remarkable growth: careful note-taking in a lab journal, insightful questions during fieldwork, or steady improvement in the data collection technique. These are achievements worth recognising!

One effective way to capture process is through progress [journals or portfolios](#). Students can collect brainstormed questions, hypothesis drafts, raw data sheets, graphs, and reflections at different stages.

By assessing the process, you send a powerful message: science is not just about the final answer, but about inquiry, perseverance, and learning from mistakes. [This encourages students to take risks, experiment, and engage more deeply, rather than play it safe for a grade.](#)

4.3.4 Supporting metacognition through citizen science

[Metacognition](#) helps students become independent learners who can adjust their strategies and keep improving.

In citizen science projects, you can nurture this simply by encouraging reflection. For example, after formulating hypotheses, you could ask, "*What part of coming up with a hypothesis was hard for you? Why do you think that is?*" Or after data collection, "*What would you do differently if you collected data again, and why?*" Questions like these push students to analyse their own methods and understanding rather than just the results.

[Learning journals are another useful tool](#). Even a short section for reflection can make a difference. Simple sentence starters such as “*Today I learned...*”, “*I’m still unsure about...*”, or “*Next time I will...*” can help younger learners express their thinking. A quick teacher comment or even a sticker shows students their reflections are valued.

Peer conversations can also prompt metacognitive insight. A simple prompt like “*Turn to your partner and share one challenge you faced and how you dealt with it*” encourages students to exchange strategies and learn from each other. As they share, you can listen in and notice who is beginning to reflect thoughtfully on their own learning.

4.3.5 Activity: How will you assess your students?

And now, over to you!

Think about the Learning Scenario you are developing and how you plan to assess student learning throughout the citizen science project. [Share your assessment ideas on the Padlet board](#), using the columns to organise your thoughts:

- **Column 1 - Assessment Design:** Which methods and assessment types will you use?
- **Column 2 – Process-Oriented Assessment:** How will you assess the *learning process* as it unfolds?
- **Column 3 – Metacognitive Strategies:** How will you help students become more aware of how they learn, set goals, monitor progress, and adapt strategies?

4.4 Finalise Your Learning Scenario

4.4.1 What’s left?

By now, with the previous units on **communicating scientific findings** and **assessment in citizen science projects**, you should have most of the tools you need to finalise your Learning Scenario.

The only part of the template we haven’t explored yet is the “**STEM Strategy Criteria.**”

Curious to know what this involves?

Let's find out!

4.4.2 The STEM Criteria

The **STEM Strategy Criteria** is a self-assessment tool designed to help you reflect on and strengthen your STEM activities —both in the classroom and across the school. It highlights the key elements of effective STEM integration and provides specific criteria for each one.

To fulfil this part in your Learning Scenario, you need to **tick at least one criterion for each key element** that your scenario addresses. This means reviewing the criteria and identifying where your Learning Scenario meets them. For example, one key element might be *“Inquiry-based science education”* with criteria like *“Students engage in formulating questions”* – your citizen science project likely checks that box!

You do **not** need to write lengthy explanations for each criterion in the template (explanations are optional). **Simply ensure you have marked at least one relevant criterion under each key element category.** This serves as a reflective checklist to see how well-rounded your scenario is in terms of good STEM practices. It might even give you ideas for small additions or tweaks to make your scenario stronger.

For more details on the key elements and their criteria, [check out the document here](#).

4.5 Live Event: TeachMeet

Date: Thursday, 6 November, 17:00 CET.

A TeachMeet is an informal way of sharing ideas, good practices, lesson plans, etc. It is also a great way to network with other teachers and educators!

During the TeachMeet you will not only get to exchange with your peers, but we will share best practices and great ideas for your Learning Scenario. In the end of this TeachMeet, you will also have the chance to ask questions to the speakers.

[You can download the presentation slides here.](#)

[The TeachMeet recording is available here.](#)

4.6 Introduction to Peer Assessment

Peer assessment or peer review activities are a central element of European Schoolnet Academy courses. On the one hand, these activities are the **only way that learning on MOOCs can be more substantively and qualitatively validated.** On the other hand, they are a mechanism for you to receive more **personalised feedback** on the work you do as part of the course.

Beyond this, the concept of peer assessment among teachers is an important idea in itself that we aim to promote with our courses. In many countries, **teachers still rarely engage in a process of peer review. Observing colleagues and giving them feedback is not necessarily a common thing for most teachers. Unlike in the academic community, where peer review is one of the main methods for validating the quality of an academic's work and supporting its further development, there is nothing equivalent in the teaching community.**

However, we know from research that reviewing someone else's work can be a powerful learning mechanism, and exchanging pedagogical practices and ideas with peers is an effective way to develop your practice. Therefore, by using peer assessment activities on our courses, **we aim to introduce and normalise the concept of peer review in the teaching community.**

"Evidence suggests that the use of peer assessment in teacher education & training has the potential to induce a shift of teachers' beliefs away from teacher-centred pedagogies to more student-centred approaches."

(Topping 2020)

A third and equally important reason why we use peer assessment on European Schoolnet Academy courses is because there is a substantial body of evidence that highlights **benefits of engaging in a peer assessment process for the learner**. Go to the next unit for a video that outlines some of these benefits.

4.6.1 Peer assessment benefits and guidance on how to approach it

Take a look at the following video, which outlines some of the benefits of using peer assessment, as well as offering **some initial advice on how to give feedback as part of the peer assessment**. While the context of the video is different from our setting, almost all of its points are equally valid for this course.

4.6.2 How to assess your peers' work

You might be asking how we can provide each other feedback if **we come from very different contexts**, e.g., teaching different age groups and subjects. Of course, it is important to **keep such differences in mind** when providing feedback for your peer. However, this **diversity of contexts can also be a key strength** of the feedback offered. An “outsider” can often see opportunities and challenges which an “insider” no longer notices. Many pedagogical practices that work at primary school level can also work at secondary level and vice versa, even if slight adaptations might be necessary. And by learning from peers teaching other subjects, we can develop a more cross-curricular perspective on our own teaching.

So how to go about giving feedback to your peers? [Here is some more concrete guidance on how to approach the assessment of your peers' work.](#)

4.6.3 Practice peer assessment

Before proceeding with the actual peer assessment, let us first carry out a short practice assessment. [Take a look at the activity here*](#). Make sure to read the full lesson description at the top first, and then focus on the activity shown.

**This is an adapted and shortened activity taken from a lesson plan developed by Barış Ertuğrul. The original lesson plan can be accessed here: <https://v.gd/HI5vV0>*

Q1: Learning Objectives

Go through each of the categories and identify to what extent the lesson plan above masters the particular aspects.

1. Is the lesson well aligned with the general learning objectives?

- a) Improvement necessary – No learning objectives have been defined.
- b) Some level of mastery – The lesson does not link with the defined learning objectives.
- c) High level of mastery – The lesson partly links with the defined learning objectives.
- d) Excellent level of mastery – The lesson clearly links with the defined learning objectives.

Constructive Feedback for Q1: Learning Objectives

In the comment box below, please explain why you selected that option for this criterion. Please keep in mind that you need to provide constructive feedback to your peer, and your answer cannot be shorter than 200 characters.

Q2 : Implementation

Is the lesson **clear, relevant and appropriate** and thereby **ready for implementation**?

- a) Improvement necessary – The lesson is not at all clear, appropriate in length nor appropriate for the age group indicated. A comprehensive redrafting is required for it to be implemented.
- b) Some level of mastery – The lesson is only in parts clear, appropriate in length and appropriate for the age group indicated. It requires substantial adjustments to be implemented.
- c) High level of mastery – The lesson is mostly clear, appropriate in length and appropriate for the age group indicated. With minor adjustments it can be implemented.
- d) Excellent level of mastery – The lesson is fully clear, appropriate in length and appropriate for the age group indicated. It can be implemented without any further development.

Constructive Feedback for Q2: Implementation

In the comment box below, please explain why you selected that option for this criterion. Please keep in mind that you need to provide constructive feedback to your peer, and your answer cannot be shorter than 200 characters.

4.7 Peer Assessment Activity

!! The final peer-to-peer activity has **3 steps**, to be completed in order. Each next step will become available when you finish the previous one. But remember, the deadline to finish the peer-to-peer activity (including your response and peer assessment) is **Wednesday, 16 November at 23:59 CET**. If you have any questions about the peer assessment, please

visit [Knowledgebase / Peer review section](#) or post your questions in the dedicated [Discussion Category "Peer Assessment Support"](#).

Before we start, we want to remind you that as a participant in this course, we expect to see your own unique ideas shine through! If you wish, feel free to use AI tools just like you would seek a friend's help – for discussing ideas or proofreading. The key is to keep your thoughts original while acknowledging how AI can enhance your learning journey. However, it is crucial to use AI responsibly and ethically which means that you need to adjust the AI-generated output to ensure the work is yours and suits your context and objectives, rather than merely copying and pasting the AI-generated answer. Furthermore, if you use AI, it is essential to disclose how it has been used to whoever sees the output, unless the final result is significantly edited and can be considered an entirely new work. Please be aware that if these rules are not followed, the submitted work may count as a case of plagiarism which will result in disqualification from receiving the certificate. Any suspected misuse of AI will be carefully investigated by our team upon which a decision will be reached and communicated to any affected users.

Step 1 – Submit Your Learning Scenario

Over the last weeks, we have guided you to work on your learning scenario. By now, you should have finished filling in all parts. If you have not completed your Learning Scenario yet, please, do so now. Your Learning Scenario **must be in English**, otherwise, it will not qualify for the course certificate.

Important note: To upload your learning scenario please follow these steps:

1. Below the responses field, select **Choose Files**.
2. In the dialog box that opens, select the file that you want to upload, and then select **Open**.
3. In the box next to your document, enter a written description of the document. This step is required to help learners understand and evaluate your learning scenario. The Upload file button will not activate until you enter a description in the **Describe field**.
4. Across from the Choose Files button, select **Upload file**.

5. You can delete files once they've been uploaded by clicking the "Delete File" button next to each uploaded file.
6. When you have finished uploading your learning scenario, select **Submit your response and move to the next step**. Then click **OK** on the dialog box to confirm.

Step 2 - Review Peers' Learning Scenarios

In this section, we ask you to review the work of your course peers [through the rubric that we had a closer look at in Module 1](#). As you know, the rubric consists of several criteria, a set of options for each criterion and a text box for written feedback. Go through each of the categories and identify to what extent the activity masters the particular aspects.

It is crucial that you **provide fair, encouraging and helpful feedback** that allows your peers to improve their LS. When you review a Learning Scenario, you evaluate each criterion, select (X) the option that best describes how well the response met that criterion and provide **written feedback** for each criterion. Please have a look at ["How to provide constructive feedback"](#) first. In the text box explain why you choose that level of mastery. What areas would you identify as strengths? What areas do you feel could be improved? What would you like to know more about?

Important note: the peer assessment activity is a time for you to share your LS and to provide **constructive feedback to your peers**. Therefore, feedback such as "Thank you", "Well done", "Congrats", etc. is not constructive feedback and as such is **not eligible for the course certificate**. Additionally, your **feedback has to be in English**, otherwise, it will not qualify for the course certificate. Like in the practice peer assessment, you need to provide constructive feedback to your peer, and your answer **should not be shorter than 200 characters for each criteria**.

If one of the works you have been assigned to review is of low quality, missing, plagiarised or otherwise non-compliant with the instructions, please select **"No"** in response to the final rubric question, "In general, does the activity meet the aforementioned requirements?" Then the course team will evaluate your colleague's submission and possibly withhold their certificate.

You will need to **review 3 Learning Scenarios of your peers**. You will receive your peers' Learning Scenarios one by one, meaning, once you review the first Learning Scenario, the second will become available. Once you are done

evaluating the second Learning Scenario, the third Learning Scenario will become available.

Step 3 - The Feedback From Your Peers

When the peer review is complete (that is, when you have finished evaluating all three Learning Scenarios), you can see the feedback you received from the peers who reviewed your Learning Scenario.

You have done an amazing job until here! Good luck with the Peer Assessment Activity!

4.8 Congratulations! What's Next?

4.8.1 Activity: Celebrate and reflect on your journey

Before we close, take a moment to reflect and share your experience with the group.

[On the Padlet](#), create a short post that includes:

- **One surprise** – something unexpected you learned or discovered in the course.
- **One proud moment** – what you're most proud of achieving during this course.
- **One wish** – something you hope your students will gain from citizen science.

4.8.2 Exciting opportunities ahead!

While this course is coming to a close, your journey with citizen science is just beginning – and there are exciting opportunities waiting for you!

2026 STEM Discovery Campaign

The [STEM Discovery Campaign](#), led by [Scientix®](#), is an international initiative that brings together schools, universities, libraries, youth clubs, and organisations from across Europe and beyond to celebrate STEM education and careers.

In 2026, you can take part by submitting the **citizen science Learning Scenario you developed during this MOOC** – with the chance to win prizes through a **special Citizen Science Award!**

The campaign will run from February to April 2026. Follow Scientix on social media or subscribe to the [Scientix Digest](#) to stay updated.

Become a Scientix Ambassador!

Did you know that completing **this course helps you meet one of the requirements for becoming a Scientix Ambassador?**

The [Scientix Ambassadors](#) are a tight-knit, diverse, and enthusiastic community of STEM educators at all levels, now boasting over 1,500 members across 50 countries! United by their passion for STEM in education, Scientix Ambassadors share Scientix activities at the national level and play an active role in supporting innovation in STEM education in their respective countries.

Their work is essential for expanding and strengthening a community committed to sharing effective classroom practices in STEM and ensuring that students are equipped with the necessary skills.

The next call for Scientix Ambassadors opens in January 2026! Follow Scientix on social media to stay updated.

Connect with CROPS

Don't forget to follow the [CROPS website and social media channels \(and subscribe to our newsletter!\)](#) to stay up to date with our activities.

And finally, a heartfelt thank you for being part of this course – and for playing an essential role in the CROPS mission to inspire young generations and strengthen the impact of citizen science across Europe!

4.8.3 Congratulations!

 Congratulations – you've completed the CROPS MOOC: Addressing Societal Challenges with Citizen Science! If you have met all the course requirements before the deadline, then you should see a **“Request certificate”** button at the top of your Progress tab. Simply click that button to get your certificate.

Still catching up? Don't worry – you have until **Wednesday, 19 November 2025, 23:59 CET** to finish your scenario and peer reviews to qualify.

We hope this learning journey has been both inspiring and practical. By bringing citizen science into your classroom, you're giving students the tools to ask questions, think critically, and take part in shaping solutions to

today's challenges. Some of them may even become the scientists of tomorrow!

Wishing you every success in your future teaching and citizen science adventures 🙌🔬🌍

Well done!

